

Translation Studies MA Dissertation

MA in Translation Studies
Distance Learning

Assignment Cover Sheet

Student Registration Number	UP831364	
Course Title	MA Translation Studies (DL)	
Module Title	Dissertation/ Major Project MA Translation Studies (DL)	
Assessment Type	Dissertation	
Assignment Title	<p>Are Language Documentation translated texts multi-purpose? A survey of macro- and micro-level strategies used in the translation of endangered languages in the field of Language Documentation.</p>	
Module Co-ordinator / Tutor	Dr. Begoña Rodríguez de Céspedes/	
Actual Date of Submission	1/10/2021	
Due Date of Submission	1/10/2021	Word Count (must be completed) 16199

Candidates are reminded that the following are defined as Assessment Offences and will be dealt with in accordance with the University's Code of Student Discipline:

any attempt to complete an assessment by means considered to be unfair; plagiarism, which the University defines as the incorporation by a student in work for assessment of material which is not their own, in the sense that all or a substantial part of the work has been copied without any adequate attempt at attribution, or has been incorporated as if it were the student's own work when in fact it is wholly or substantially the work of another person or persons.

Are Language Documentation translated texts multi-purpose?

A survey of macro- and micro-level strategies used in the translation of endangered languages in the field of Language Documentation.

Holly Drayton

A dissertation submitted in partial fulfilment of the MA in Translation Studies

School of Languages and Applied Linguistics, University of Portsmouth

October, 2021

ABSTRACT

A central aim of the field of Language Documentation is the creation and storage of 'lasting, multi-purpose' collections of endangered language audio-visual texts, with accompanying translations (Himmelman, 2006, p.2). Despite many important developments in the field over the last two decades, to our best knowledge, there has been no systematic attempt to research or theorise the translation processes and resulting translated texts involved in language documentation work. Therefore, this dissertation presents the results of two studies on current practices in the translation of language documentation texts: Language Documentation Translation (LDT). Firstly, a corpus study was conducted which examined 1088 endangered language texts, from 10 deposits in the Endangered Languages Archive (ELAR) to determine the macro-level translation decisions taken by language documentation researchers. Second, a smaller corpus of 16 endangered language texts, accompanied by glossing and English translations, was surveyed to determine the micro-level translation strategies used to render cultural terms in the semantic domains of *People, Place, Food, Ecology, Measurements* and *Cultural objects/practices*. The findings are analysed to determine whether current practices are producing translated texts that are truly 'multi-purpose' and useful to their intended audiences: community members, language learners, wider academic users and beyond.

Table of Contents

1. Introduction	1
2. Literature Review.....	3
2.1. Overview of Language Documentation	3
2.1.1. Defining Endangered Languages	3
2.1.2. Language Documentation : Practice and output.....	3
2.1.3. Ethical Language Documentation	4
2.2. Language Documentation Translation: What does the literature tell us?.....	5
2.2.1. How are Language Documentation Translated texts used?	5
2.2.2. How useful are Language Documentation Translated Texts (LD TTs)?	6
2.2.3. Challenges of Language Documentation Translation	8
2.3. Translation Studies: Frameworks for Language Documentation Translation.....	10
2.3.1. Translation Paradigms.....	10
2.4. Translation Methods and Strategies for Language Documentation Translation	13
2.4.1. Translating Culture	13
2.4.2. Macro-Level Translation	14
2.4.3. Micro-Level Translation Strategies	15
2.5. Research Aims and Questions.....	18
3. Research Methodology	20
3.1. Study 1: Macro-level Translation Methods	20
3.1.1. Data.....	20
3.1.2. Variables	22
3.1.3. Limitations	25
3.2. Study 2: Micro-level translation strategies in LDT	26
3.2.1. Data.....	26
3.2.2. Variables	27
3.2.3. Limitations	30
4. Results.....	31
4.1. Macro-level Methods.....	31
4.1.1. Transcription, Translation and Glossing.....	31
4.1.2. Genre.....	32
4.1.3. Languages of translated texts	34
4.1.4. Translator acknowledgement	36
4.2. Micro-level translation strategies used to render cultural terms.....	37
4.2.1. Strategies	37
3.2.2. Strategies according to deposit	40
5. Discussion	42
5.1. Macro-level Translation decisions	42
5.1.1. Macro-Level Methods used in LDT	42
5.2. Micro-Level Strategies	48
5.2.1. Retention	49
5.2.2. Specification	51
5.2.3. Direct Translation	53
5.2.4. Generalisation.....	54
5.2.5. Linguistic Substitution	54

Translation Studies MA Dissertation

5.2.6. Official Equivalent.....	56
5.2.8. Strategies by Deposit: The effect of the translator	57
6. Conclusion.....	58
6.1. What does the investigation into translation of cultural terms reveal about macro- and micro-level strategies in LDT?	58
References.....	61
Appendices.....	70
Appendix 1 – Guide to ELAR references	70
Appendix 2: ELAR Deposits surveyed for Study 1.....	71
Appendix 3: List of references for the text corpus for Study 2.....	72
Appendix 4 – Sample of Translation Strategies used for rendering Cultural Terms	74
Appendix 5: Sample Source Text.....	81

List of Tables, Figures and Examples

Table 1: Year of deposits.....	21
Table 2: Distribution of languages	21
Table 3: Distributions of affiliated institutions	22
Table 4: Simplified Genres	24
Table 5: Languages of Translated Texts.....	25
Table 6: Features of corpus texts.....	26
Table 7: Cultural Domains Represented in the research corpus	28
Table 8: Strategies for rendering cultural terms (based on Pedersen, 2011)	29
Table 9: Percentage of transcription, translation and glossing by deposit	31
Table 10: Percentage of transcribed, translated and glossed texts by genre.	33
Table 11: Percentage of TTs by language	34
Table 12: : Translator acknowledgement	36
Table 13: Translation strategies by domain.....	37
Table 14: Combined Strategies	39
Table 15: Translation strategies by deposit.....	40
Figure 1: Percentage of Transcription, Translation and Glossing by deposit.	32
Figure 2: Translation and Glossing by genre.....	33
Figure 3: Languages of translated texts (%).....	35
Figure 4: Translation strategies by deposit (%)	41
Example 1.....	30
Example 2.....	43
Example 3.....	47
Example 4.....	47

List of Abbreviations

ELAR	Endangered Languages Archive
LD	Language documentation
LDT	Language documentation translation
SC	Source culture
SL	Source language
ST	Source text
TC	Target culture
TL	Target language
TT	Target text

1. Introduction

This dissertation presents the results obtained in two studies aiming to describe the micro- and macro-level translation strategies of language documentation (LD) researchers working to create audio-visual and textual records of endangered languages.

In light of the crisis facing speakers of around half of the languages spoken around the world, LD is a field of linguistics that is concerned with recording, processing and archiving audio and/or audio-visual endangered language texts. The aim is to create “lasting, multi-purpose records” (Himmelmann, 2006, p. 2), that can be used by a range of different audiences, including speakers of the endangered language, and people who do not understand the language, both in the present day and in the future.

It is acknowledged within the LD literature that translation is an important element in facilitating or denying access to the texts, since many of the potential users do not understand the endangered source language (Beier, 2015). However, there has been little attempt to theorise or offer guidance on translation methods and strategies within the field, resulting in a situation where many LD texts are deemed to be unsuitable for use outside of the original research project, due to lack of appropriate material, or poor-quality translation (Evans & Sasse, 2007; Penfield & Tucker, 2011; Austin, 2017, p.35).

In view of the implications of translation decisions on whether LD texts are truly useful in multiple contexts, particularly the key areas of potential use, language revitalisation through language learning, academic use, and use in the wider world, this dissertation aims to provide data to determine:

1. What are the macro-level translation strategies used in LDT?
2. What are the micro-level translation strategies used in LDT?
3. Do these strategies contribute to the creation of multi-purpose texts?

Translation Studies MA Dissertation

To answer these questions, two corpus-based studies were conducted. The first study examines 1088 endangered language texts from 10 deposits with ELAR (The Endangered Languages Archive) in order to provide answers for research questions 1 and 3 by identifying the macro-level translation decisions made regarding which texts to translate and/or gloss, and which not to translate and/or gloss, which language(s) to use for the translated texts (TTs) and who worked on the translation. The second study aims to provide data to answer research questions 2 and 3 by closely examining the strategies used to render 422 cultural term 'triplets', comprising of original endangered language source text term, associated gloss and translated text rendering, in 16 texts, following the Descriptive Translation Studies method (Toury 1995), and Pedersen's (2011) taxonomy of translation strategies.

This dissertation is structured as follows. First, Chapter 2 presents a Literature Review, with particular reference to the role of translation within Language Documentation (LD). Second, Chapter 3 describes the Methodology of the two studies. Third, in Chapter 4, the results are presented. Chapter 5 presents a discussion of the results in terms of their implications on the potential uses of the texts. Finally, the most relevant conclusions are established in Chapter 6.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Overview of Language Documentation

2.1.1. Defining Endangered Languages

Around half of the world's 7000 languages are likely to stop being spoken in the 21st century (Himmelman, 1998, 2006; Austin, 2010; Grenoble, 2010; Woodbury, 2003, 2011; Robins & Uhlenbeck, 1991, Hale *et al.*, 1992). As a result, growing numbers of languages all over the world are being spoken by decreasing and aging populations, in reducing numbers of domains, and are not being passed down to the next generation of speakers (Austin, 2016, p. 148). The process of linguicide, whereby languages and their speakers, are oppressed or exterminated "takes various forms including language bans, "language death" (due to natural death, migration, political suppressions), and 'linguicism'" (Salih, 2019, p. 36; Skutnabb-Kangas, 2000). The widely used term, *endangered languages*, has been criticised as objectifying languages, minimising the sociological and political contexts of language loss, and erasing the agency of speech communities (Roche, 2020). While terms such as *minority* or *lesser-spoken* are also used to describe oppressed languages, they do not convey the urgency with which the most oppressed languages are being lost since they can refer equally to robust languages with lower numbers of speakers. Indeed, Cronin (2019, p. 336) notes that 'almost all languages other than English have now become minor languages in the translation research community'. Therefore, due to the lack of a widely used alternative, this research uses the term *endangered language(s)*.

2.1.2. Language Documentation: Practice and output

In response to the crisis facing the world's languages and their speech communities, the field of Language Documentation (LD) has developed over the past two decades, with the aim of creating "lasting, multi-purpose records" of the linguistic practices of speech communities by collecting linguistic data, in audio(-visual) and annotated formats (Himmelman, 2006, p. 2). In order to ensure that the resulting outputs, or documentary corpora, are multi-purpose, the audio-visual material is processed and presented in a way that affords access to a range of different potential users, including speakers and people who do not speak the language (Himmelman, 2006, p.11). Therefore, for many potential

users of the documented texts, translation and annotation are vital to allow the content to be accessible and usable. To meet this need, LD researchers are encouraged to create documentary corpora that includes transcription, grammatical glossing and/or translation into one or more languages.

2.1.3. Ethical Language Documentation

There has been much recent discussion about ethical practices and the need for Indigenous rights to be centred within LD (Stibbe, 2020; De Korne & Leonard, 2017; Dobrin, Austin & Nathan, 2009) by advocating practices that focus on increasing language rights and supporting revitalisation initiatives to increase the number of speakers of a language and/or the range of domains in which it is used (Fishman, 1991, 2001; Hinton & Hale, 2001; Hornberger, 2010; Hinton, 2011; Romaine, 2007; Grenoble & Whaley, 2006). To this effect, training, handbooks and research have been developed to promote LD practices that support and empower endangered language communities. These include ensuring that linguistic data is collected and processed (e.g. transcribed, glossed and translated) with revitalisation in mind (Grenoble, 2013 p. 46; Cope & Penfield, 2011; Czaykowska-Higgins, 2009).

However, there has been very little discussion, theorisation or guidance offered on translation methods and strategies within the field. For example, a thorough search of the LD literature from the past two decades reveals just two published articles focussing on translating LD texts (see Woodbury, 2007; Evans & Sasse, 2007), both of which present case studies of the challenges that the researchers have experienced in translating as part of their work in the field¹. Furthermore, a talk given by Beier (2015) identifies the lack of attention given to translation and outlines some of the issues, with a call to researchers in the field to bring new focus to the translation of language documentation texts. In addition, it has been reported that existing LD translated texts are often unsuitable for use for revitalisation initiatives within the communities that they are intended to serve (Evans & Sasse, 2007; Hinton, 2011; Penfield & Tucker, 2011; Rice, 2011).

Therefore, in order for LD to be successful in supporting increased language rights and revitalization initiatives, there is an urgent need for research into translation practices, as well as development and theorization to improve the suitability of translated texts for their target audiences and uses. The next section explores the potential uses and audiences of LD translated texts.

2.2. Language Documentation Translation: What does the literature tell us?

2.2.1. How are Language Documentation Translated texts used?

Three main uses for ‘multi-purpose’ LD Translated Texts (TT) have been identified:

1. Use within the language community (present and future) e.g. revitalisation through language learning; preserving and passing on cultural knowledge.
2. Academic use (present and future) in the field of linguistics, wider academic fields, and to support open science notions of verifiability, replicability and reproducibility (Olalla-Soller, 2020; Berez-Kroeker *et al.* 2017; Gawne *et al.* 2017).
3. Use in the wider world – e.g. to aid the understanding and development of new ways of thinking, living and being (Cronin, 2017, 2020; Stibbe, 2020, p.193); in addition to imparting traditional knowledge, in areas such as, ‘medicinal plants, food cultivation, irrigation techniques, navigation systems, seasonal calendars’ (Rymer, 2012)².

² To illustrate, a recent study (Cámara-Leret & Bascompte, 2021) reports that 75% of all medicinal plants are only known to one language, meaning that the knowledge disappears with the language.

2.2.2. How useful are Language Documentation Translated Texts (LD TTs)?

2.2.2.1. Potential Users

As mentioned, many of the users of LD TTs, including members of the language community who have not had the language passed down to them, do not speak or understand the endangered language (O'Shannesey *et al.*, 2019; Czaykowska-Higgins, 2009; Schwartz & Dobrin, 2016). Therefore, in order for the texts to be accessible and useful, quality annotation – that is, transcription, glossing and translation - is essential (Austin, 2013, p. 6; Nathan & Austin, 2004). In fact, language documentation material that is not accompanied by adequate annotation has been described as “as helpful as tablets in the Indus or other undeciphered script”, in that users may know it is an example of linguistic use, but cannot gain further information from the text alone (Evans & Sasse, 2007, p. 60). In other words, endangered language texts may be carefully recorded and archived, but without sufficient annotation, they cannot be used by any potential audience outside of the initial documentation project (Penfield & Tucker, 2011, p. 292). This has implications on open science since any research based on linguistic data that cannot be understood cannot be verified, replicated or reproduced (Olalla-Soller, 2020; Berez-Kroeker *et al.* 2017; Gawne *et al.* 2017). Since numbers of speakers are dwindling, in most cases it will become impossible to re-record endangered language linguistic data, rendering this an urgent issue.

2.2.2.2. LD Translated Texts

Two key features have been identified as important in facilitating or hindering the use of LD texts for their intended purposes: existence of appropriate texts and quality of annotation.

For language learning – a primary activity for those wanting to increase the number of speakers and domains of language use (Taylor-Adams, 2019, p. 428), texts are needed that demonstrate “a rich language environment” (Underriner *et al.*, 2021, p. 237) and provide examples of functional language such as, “how conversations are organised in the particular community, how to use language to get people to do things, what is appropriate to say or

Translation Studies MA Dissertation

not say in what situation, how to agree, disagree, or argue with someone, and how to be a functioning speaker of the language “ (Austin, 2021, p.202). However, this kind of language is often lacking from documentation corpora (Sallabank & King, 2021, p.35), and where corpora do contain a range of genres, translation tends to be prioritised for texts that are relevant to the researcher’s interests – possibly texts containing “interesting or unusual linguistic features” (Austin, 2016, p.161), which are not suited to language learning. For example, Marnie Atkins, a speech community linguist working to revitalise her heritage language using an academic linguist’s texts and recordings stated that she ‘wishes there had been more functionally useful language recorded. “I would like to be able to say, “good morning” in my language, but I can’t find that in the texts”’ (Marnie Atkins, as cited in Yamada, 2011, p.4). Similarly, the availability of a range of texts and genres – accompanied by the necessary annotation - is essential for facilitating present and future academic use in a range of fields and broader use.

The quality of annotation accompanying documentary texts has also been reported to affect use. Firstly, texts may be glossed and translated into languages that are not relevant to the local linguistic ecology, and therefore not accessible to the local language community (Taylor-Adams, 2019). Furthermore, where provided in an accessible language, translations may be ‘unclear, incomplete, or wrong’ (Evans & Sasse, 2007), and ‘cryptic glossing or wrong glosses’ may be found when ‘the author could not understand their language consultant’s accent or pronunciation, or because the semantics of the source language terms were misunderstood’. (Austin, 2017, p.35). Errors in LD translation or glossing have been linked to ambiguity of words that can express more than one meaning, lack of full correspondence between the ST and TT with no translator notes explaining additions or subtractions, lack of contextual information and the impossibility of recovering missing information due to the urgency of language endangerment contexts where many speakers are elderly and may have died since the documentation was carried out (Beier, 2015).

It is clear that LDTTs are often not suitable for the needs of their target audiences and purposes; or, simply the appropriate texts are not translated. Evidently, more research is required in order to work towards developing language documentation translation output

to better support the field of language documentation in meeting its key aims of improved language rights, fostering academic research and thereby ensuring LD texts are truly ‘multi-purpose’.

2.2.3. Challenges of Language Documentation Translation

In addition to identifying problems with the quality and (lack of) production of LD TTs, the LD literature suggests some possible causes: lack of translation training, guidance and resources and cultural differences.

2.2.3.1. Lack of Training, Guidance and Resources

LD researchers do not routinely receive translation training in university programs in LD or Field Methods courses³. Furthermore, there is “astonishingly little” published guidance on LDT (Beier, 2015). To illustrate, as highlighted by Beier (2015), in several key Language Documentation handbooks, the term *translation* does not appear in the index (e.g. the 545-page Oxford Handbook of Linguistic Fieldwork, (Thieberger, 2012) and the 340-page book Language Documentation: Practice and Values (Grenoble & Furbee, 2010). Furthermore, although it is acknowledged that professional translation is an important skill, art or science that requires training (Schultze-Berndt, 2006, p.232), the general impression from the LD literature is that translation is work that researchers are expected to carry out, almost as an afterthought to the principal activity of data collection, with, at best, “no, or minimal, theory and methodological guidance” (Beier, 2015). Acknowledging a lack of confidence in translation practices in the field, it has been suggested that LD researchers not attempt to “meet the standards of professional literary or scientific translation” and that therefore, LDT should be considered as providing no more than a “clue” to the meaning of the original text (Schultze-Berndt, 2006, p.232). This perspective does not appear to support or encourage the production of translated texts that are able to meet the requirements of their target audiences and uses.

³ E.g. Specialist programs offered at The University of Hawai'i at Manoa and SOAS, University of London; In addition to workshops and summer schools such as FieldLing, held in Paris.

More widely, beyond the field of Language Documentation, translator training initiatives rarely include minority or endangered languages due to financial unviability, low demand and lack of qualified teachers (Taibi & Ozolins, 2016). The resulting implications are that translations involving minority or endangered languages may be “poor, inappropriate or less effective” (Taibi & Ozolins, 2016, p.22). Furthermore, the lack of investment in translation skills in this area also means that endangered language contexts are absent from translation theories; and thus the cycle perpetuates.

However, Beier (2015) optimistically notes that this situation could be improved by including “good basic training in relevant aspects of translation theory”, in order to build up skills required to produce good free translations of the rich endangered language material that linguists document.

2.2.3.2. Cultural Differences and Cultural terms

Cultural differences have been identified as another barrier to LDT. ‘Culture’ is a productive area of Translation Studies, where it has been noted that translation is more straightforward when conducted between two languages that are more culturally similar and less culturally distant (House, 2016). In the case of LDT, cultural distances tend to be great, and in many cases the endangered language culture is not well-known to the linguist researcher before documentation.

To illustrate, in Dalabon, an endangered language of Australia, the term, *dalabborrod*, means, “place on a tree where the branches rub together, taken advantage of in sorcery by placing something that has been in contact with the victim, such as clothes, in such a way that it will be rubbed as the tree blows in the wind, gradually sickening and weakening the victim” (Evans & Sasse, 2007, p.63). There is no equivalent concept in anglophone cultures, let alone an equivalent lexical item, which brings a challenge to the translation process (Baker, 2018).

Thus, concepts that are culturally significant and linguistically coded in one language community, may not be present in other language communities and cultures, making translation challenging. Although LD researchers have identified this potential challenge to translation, there has so far been little attempt to establish methods or strategies to deal with the translation of cultural entities and terms.

2.3. Translation Studies: Frameworks for Language Documentation Translation

Section 3 turns to the translation studies (TS) literature and existing frameworks that are relevant to LDT.

Within the field of TS, endangered language translation is an under-researched area. There have been calls for increased inclusivity in the field, including broadening the field of research to include lesser-studied and endangered languages and cultural perspectives (Bassnett & Johnston, 2019; Cronin 2017; Tymoczko, 2007, 2009). However, this has, so far, not materialised in empirical research in endangered language translation. Over the last 3 decades developments in TS have emerged that are particularly useful for situating LDT. Therefore, three key research areas, *The Cultural Turn*, *The Outward Turn* and *Translator visibility*, are presented below.

2.3.1. Translation Paradigms

2.3.1.1. The Cultural Turn

The importance of culture to translation is well established, and awareness of the existence of cultural asymmetries and “untranslatable” cultural terms has been discussed in the TS literature since the middle of the 20th century (e.g. Jakobsen, 1959). Furthermore, since the Cultural Turn_ in translation studies in the late 1980s and early 1990s (e.g. Snell-Hornby 1988; Bassnett & Lefevere, 1990), translation has been conceptualised as a process that occurs between two cultures, involving “cross-cultural transfer” (Snell-Hornby, 1988, p.39-64), and, as such, translating cultural referents has been identified as the area of translation

requiring the most skill (Katan & Taibi, 2021; Cronin, 2003; Pedersen, 2011). It has been suggested that translators are cultural mediators (Hatim & Mason, 1990; Pym, 2000, p.191; Cronin, 2003; Katan & Taibi, 2021) since they must be aware of the cultural context of both source language and target audience, and work to make connections between and across these cultures, whether as an ‘impartial mediator’ (Hale & Liddicoat, 2015, p.19) or an empowered agent (Tymoczko, 2007).

2.3.1.2. The Outward Turn

Although the relationship between culture and translation has been a productive area of research in TS, there has been a tendency to use examples from Eurocentric contexts, whilst “avoiding considerations of more radical cultural differences that arise from broader international scrutiny” (Tymoczko, 2007, p.225). It follows that, basing theories of translating culture on examples between modern European languages, where the degree of cultural difference is relatively small, cannot provide the full picture. Therefore, it has been argued that there is a need for the field of translation studies to move beyond Western data, as part of broadening the role, function and definition of translation (Bassnett & Johnston, 2019; Cronin, 2017, 2020). Furthermore, Marais & Delgado Luchner (2018, p.387) argue that key TS concepts such as *language*, *translation* and *interpreting* have different meanings, shaped by different constraints than in the European context, and that further research is required to bring greater understanding of these concepts in multilingual contexts, where phenomena such as code-mixing, translanguaging, use of lingua francas and ad-hoc interpretation and translation practices are common. This research will aim to go some way to filling this gap by providing new empirical data on translating culture from endangered languages to languages of wider communication.

2.3.1.3. The Translator.

The third key area of research in TS that is highly relevant to LDT is the most recent research on *who* translates, including the notions of translator agency and visibility.

Translation scholars have argued for increased emphasis on the agency of the translator (e.g. Venuti, 1995, 1998a, 1998b; Cronin, 2006, Tymoczko, 2007; Pym, 2012, p. 56-57; Chesterman, 1997, p. 182; Baker, 2013), starting from the decision of what to translate or not translate (Pym, 2012), then continuing with decisions over what to “change, add or omit” (Chesterman, 1997, p.182). In addition, translation across cultural differences is argued to constitute “the centre of a translator’s power and agency” (Tymoczko, 2007), and that this agency can be realised as a means to fulfil the translator’s mission, which may ‘extend to social agency in the form of a contribution to education, human rights, and empowerment of disadvantaged groups’ (Katan and Taibi, 2021, p.107; see also, Inghilleri, 2008; Taibi & Ozolins, 2016; Taibi, 2018).¹ On the other hand, it has been noted that translators’ power and agency can also have negative effects by, for example, “impos[ing] new cultural configurations on an (unwilling) audience, [stealing] cultural treasures, to despoil a people of their land, [converting] a people by force to another religion” (Tymoczko, 2007). Advocacy for Translator Agency is in opposition to the ‘McDonaldisation’ of translation, as part of the move towards translation automation, where translation is perceived to be ‘automatic, invisible and instantaneous’ (Cronin 2017, p30), and produces TTs where the labour of translation is hidden (Venuti, 2008), and thus, marginalised.

Therefore, an awareness of translator agency arguably has a large impact on translated texts: if a translator understands the power and agency that they hold over their translation choices and practice, they can produce texts that are better suited to their intended audiences and purposes. However, as shown in Section 2.2, LD Translators generally do not receive training or guidance in translation, and translation work seems to be seen as a low-prestige element of Language Documentation. These factors point to a lack of awareness of their agency as translators, and therefore a lack of awareness of the political, ideological

and ethical implications of their translation choices (Beier, 2015), thus hindering success in the mission of supporting increased language justice.

2.4. Translation Methods and Strategies for Language Documentation

Translation

This section turns to the literature on translation methods and strategies that can be used in the context of translating cultural terms in LD texts. Section 2.4.1 introduces the key theoretical underpinnings of translating cultural terms. Section 2.4.2. Focusses on macro-level translation, while Section 2.4.3. Focuses on micro-level translation.

2.4.1. Translating Culture

As discussed in Section 2.3., Translation and Culture are highly interrelated and translation requires a deep understanding of both source and target cultures. Furthermore, translating culture has been identified as being one of the most challenging areas for translators, and as such, a body of research has emerged on translation methods and strategies.

Recent theories of translating culture have argued for a broad view, encompassing the text as a whole, in addition to related cultural implications (Tymoczko, 2007). Therefore, a translator uses the language output from the ST, in addition to contextual knowledge to determine the meaning. In order to communicate the meaning to the target audience, translators use various strategies to allow the cultural notions of the SC and the TC to communicate, which are selected based on their suitability depending on the context of the texts, including the translator, and the target audience (Katan & Taibi, 2021, p.154).

Therefore, TTs produced by different translators in different contexts will always differ since it is necessary to prioritise which parts of the ST to carry over to the TT, which is why awareness of translator agency is so important. This has been acknowledged by the theorisation of distinctions such as, Formal vs Dynamic Equivalence (Nida, 1964), Foreignizing vs Domesticating (Venuti, 1995), Exoticising vs Assimilating (Kwiecinski, 2001), Overt vs Covert (House, 2016) and Source-Oriented vs Target-Oriented (Pedersen, 2011), with the general idea that a translated text either brings the reader closer to the source language and culture by remaining faithful to the source text ; or to some extent erases the

source language and culture by bringing the text closer to the target language and culture. However, these binaries are, arguably, oversimplified, and calls have been made to abandon such distinctions, since, in practice, it is difficult to determine which strategy is being used and often multiple strategies are combined together (Ramière, 2006, p.157).

2.4.2. Macro-Level Translation

This section presents the key macro-level translation strategies that are relevant to LDT: Choice of text to translate, Choice of TT language(s) and Choice of translator. These elements are reflective of House's (2016) 'complexity of translation' which includes the macro-level features : translation task variables (why? Who for?), situational variables (where? When?), translator variables (who?).

2.4.2.1. Choice of Text

As shown in Section 2, the genres of LD TTs determine how and by whom they can be used: texts including functional language are more suitable for revitalization purposes, while texts containing "interesting or unusual linguistic features" (Austin, 2016, p.161) may be preferred for academic research. Furthermore, anecdotal reports by LD researchers have explained that texts that are more straightforward to annotate are often prioritised for translation, meaning that single-speaker texts, without overlapping speech, and texts where the topic is 'clearly delimited, and...known vocabulary was used' may be more likely to be selected for translation (Collins, 2019). However, these texts are unlikely to be the most suitable for community and revitalisation use. Therefore, the choice to translate (or not) allows texts to be accessed (or not) by multi-purpose audiences, illustrating the asymmetric power of LD researchers and translators, since without translation, Indigenous peoples 'are silenced potentially forever' (Cronin, 2017, p.146).

2.4.2.2. Choice of Language of TT

The choice of language for LD TTs also determines how and by whom the texts can be used. As mentioned in Section 2 many potential users of the texts do not understand the endangered source language. Therefore, texts become accessible to the local community,

and beyond, when TTs are rendered in a language that is part of the local linguistic context. Conversely, English is the most commonly used language of global academia (Bassnett & Johnston, 2019; Bennett, 2015; Apter, 2013), and therefore is likely to be the most useful language for academic purposes, as well as for allowing the texts to be useful to more people in broader applications, thus introducing the ST into broader contexts.

2.4.2.3. Choice of Translator

It has been noted that the translator's culture influences translation output (Tymoczko, 2007). For example, if the translator identifies with the SC, TC or a third culture, this has an impact on their understanding of the cultural frames involved in translation. Therefore, the choice of translator is an important element of macro-level decision-making in LDT. To illustrate the complexities, an anecdote published on the personal blog of a LD researcher (Collins, 2019) outlines the translation process in the documentation of Sasi, a language of Botswana: The speakers of the SL, also fluent in the local dominant language, are elderly and illiterate, while the translator speaks English and the local dominant language, but not the SL. Therefore, the researcher plays a recording, the SL speakers then translate their own words into the local dominant language, which are clarified and written down by the translator. The translator then translates and writes the phrase in English. In this context, the role of translator is not clearly delimited. Rather, the cultures of each of the participants in the process have an effect on the TTs, thus highlighting how the choice of translator may affect the translation output and the usefulness of the translated texts.

2.4.3. Micro-Level Translation Strategies

This section explores the micro-level translation strategies available to translators when translating, or rendering, cultural terms from one language to another, with a focus on how these strategies are relevant to LDT.

How a translator chooses to render cultural terms impacts target culture perceptions of the source culture since the choice of translation strategy may contribute to perpetuating (positive or negative) stereotypes, emphasizing or erasing cultural specificities, or causing

cross-cultural misunderstanding (Ramière, 2006, Tymoczko, 2007). Therefore, the strategies used determine the TT's potential to meet the requirements of its intended uses. In other words, even in the case of felicitous macro-level translation choices, if the translation micro-strategies used are not appropriate, the resulting TT is unlikely to be suitable for its intended audiences.

There is a large body of research on translating cultural terms (see Newmark, 1988; Hermans, 1988; Hervy & Higgins, 1992; Florin, 1993; Leppihalme, 2001; Pedersen, 2011; Baker 2018; Katan & Taibi, 2021), and an array of terminology has emerged in the TS literature to describe cultural lexical items⁴. The present research uses the more general *cultural terms*, partly to avoid confusing jargon and partly because there have been no previous empirical studies on LDT to determine the realities of the context, and allow for a narrower definition. Despite differences in terminology and definitions, the existing taxonomies tend to contain a similar number of strategies (generally 5-7) with broadly similar strategies, that are situated on a continuum from more source-oriented to more target-oriented (e.g. Taxonomies presented in Newmark, 1988; Vinay & Dalbernet, Pedersen, 2011) However, this research has yet to be extended to endangered languages. Therefore, research into the translation of cultural items from endangered languages is needed to test and challenge existing theories and to broaden the field of TS, in addition to improving the output of LDT.

2.4.3.1. Pedersen's (2011) Taxonomy

One of the most comprehensive taxonomies of strategies for translating cultural items is suggested by Pedersen (2011), and will form the basis of this analysis. The taxonomy was compiled based on data from subtitling, which, similarly to LDT, involves translating from an audio-visual source text into a time-aligned written target text. The strategies are presented below.

⁴ These include: ECR (Extra-linguistic Cultural Reference (Pedersen, 2011); CSI (Culturally Significant Item (Baker, 2018)), signature concepts (Tymoczko, 2007), CSL (Culture-Specific Lexis (Lee, 2017), cultureme (Nord 1997, p34), Cultural Words (Newmark, 1988, p93)).

1. Retention

The ST term is rendered in the TT, unchanged or slightly adapted to meet TL requirements. Retention has been argued to be the most source-oriented translation strategy, as it brings the audience of the TT closer to the SL and has been suggested as a way to achieve 'local colour' (E.g. Newmark, 1988; Baker, 2018). Retention in this context may also valorise the minority language and bring prestige to the language community by illustrating how the minority language can be used in different contexts (Sommer, 1992, p.104-5).

However, it has also been shown that, in certain uses, Retention can have an exoticising effect, where stereotypes are accentuated, and racist ideas are supported (Shamma, 2005). Therefore, it is important to understand the SC and TC contexts in order to use Retention in order to achieve the desired effects in the TT.

2. Specification

Specification describes a semantic shift where the TT item is more specific than the ST, due to more information being added, either textually or through translator notes. Specification is achieved by completing a name or acronym (Completion) or by adding more semantic content (Addition). According to Pedersen (2011), specification generally takes the form of retention + generalisation, where the original ST term is reproduced in the TT accompanied by a more general term (e.g. hypernym or paraphrase). Therefore, specification causes many of the same effects as retention, such as bringing the TT audience closer to the SC, but also provides additional information to allow the TT audience to access the referent.

3. Direct translation.

Direct translation involves only changing the language, with no semantic changes. Therefore, direct translation is expected to be used in cases of straightforward translation where equivalents are available in the TL (Pedersen, 2011).

4. Generalization

A semantic shift where the TT referent is more general than the ST, thought to involve ‘chunking up’ in terms of semantic reference (Katan and Taibi, 2021). Baker (2018, p. 25) recommends the use of hypernyms, that is, replacing the ST term with a superordinate term, as “it works equally well in most, if not all, languages, since the hierarchical structure of semantic fields is not language-specific”. However, Generalisation is a more target-oriented strategy since using a more general term necessitates losing some of the connotations of the original ST referent.

5. Substitution.

Replacing the ST term with a TC item or a better-known SC item; or with something completely different. This target-oriented strategy has been linked to ‘epistemicide’ (Bennett, 2007) whereby SC values and beliefs are forced into Anglocentric norms of discourse, resulting in the loss of meaning and enrichment.

6. Omission of the lexical item.

The ST term is not reproduced in any way in the TT, used when the information conveyed by the term is considered unnecessary to the TT audience, or peripheral to the understanding of the text. Alternatively, Baker (2018, p.234) suggests that omission may be used as a way of avoiding violating TC expectations on taboos.

7. Official Equivalent.

This strategy describes the use of a ready-made official TL Equivalent, and is reported to be common, for example, in translating European Union documentation, and for translating highly standardised entities such as weights and measures (Pedersen 2011). It is not known to what extent this strategy applies in contexts where there is a larger cultural distance between SL and TL.

2.5. Research Aims and Questions

This chapter has demonstrated the importance of LDT in allowing LD texts to be ‘multi purpose’, thereby helping to meet goals of improved language justice, as well as for academic and wider purposes. However, the LD literature has not, so far, provided

Translation Studies MA Dissertation

guidance on LDT and, therefore, translation output has been reported to be unsuitable for the required purposes and audiences. There is a clear need for empirical research to reveal the true state of current translation practices in LD, to provide a starting point to improve translation output. Furthermore, there is a clear need for more research into endangered languages in order to broaden understanding and test existing TS theories.

Therefore, this dissertation aims to fill these gaps by providing empirical data illustrating macro- and micro-level strategies of translating cultural terms in LTD, and analysing whether current practices support the production of texts that can be used by their intended audiences: language communities, academia and the wider world. Furthermore, this analysis will test existing theories of translating cultural terms, in the under-researched area of endangered languages.

This research aims to answer:

1. What are the macro-level translation methods used in LDT?
2. What are the micro-level translation strategies used in LDT?
3. Do these strategies contribute to the creation of multi-purpose texts?

3. Research Methodology

Chapter 2 identified 2 major gaps: a lack of research in language documentation translation (LDT) and a lack of empirical research into the translation of cultural terms outside of Eurocentric contexts. This research aims to fill these gaps by conducting studies to reveal:

1. The macro-level methods used in language documentation translation.
2. Micro-level strategies used to render cultural terms in language documentation translation.
3. Whether these strategies contribute to the creation of multi-purpose texts.

Chapter 3 presents the research methodology including the datasets, and the features for analysis.

3.1. Study 1: Macro-level Translation Methods

3.1.1. Data

The first study, which aims to answer research questions 1 and 3, surveys ten deposits from the Endangered Languages Archive (ELAR), which are freely accessible through the ELAR website⁵. ELAR deposits are collections of audio(-visual) texts of spoken endangered languages, accompanied by bundles of related text files and/or images. The text files generally contain annotations of the socio-linguistic conditions of the recordings and their participants, transcription, translation and grammatical glossing. Ten deposits were selected as the largest corpus size that could be handled within the constraints of the MA dissertation project, while being a large enough sample to give an impression of practices within LDT in a range of research contexts.

The deposits were created between 2015-2021 (See Table 1) and therefore, provide a picture of the most current practices. Only deposits that have been promoted by ELAR as 'closed' were included, as this aimed to ensure that the depositors were not planning to

⁵ <https://www.elararchive.org>.

amend their work. Although, since ELAR collections are dynamic, it is still possible that the deposits will be updated or modified in the future (Salffner, 2015, p.248).

Table 1: Year of deposits

Year	Number of deposits
2015	1
2017	1
2018	3
2019	1
2020	3
2021	1
Total	10

The ten deposits include texts recorded in ten languages spoken in different countries, representing areas with high levels of linguistic diversity (Table 2). They have been deposited by researchers affiliated with academic institutions in a range of countries (Table 3), skewed towards the USA, Europe and Australia/New Zealand, which are areas where funding and expertise on Language Documentation are centred.

Table 2: Distribution of languages

Country (a-z)	Number of deposits
China	1
Colombia	1
India	1
Indonesia	1
Nepal	1
Paraguay	1
Papua New Guinea	2
Vanuatu	2
Total	10

Table 3: Distributions of affiliated institutions

Country (a-z)	Number of deposits
Australia	1
France	1
Germany	2
New Zealand	1
UK	1
USA	4
Total	10

The audio(-visual) files were extracted from the 10 deposits, producing a data set of 1088 endangered language texts, plus accompanying annotations, transcriptions and/or translations.⁶ The full bibliographic list of deposits used in this survey is given in Appendix 2.

3.1.2. Variables

The 1088 texts were coded in Microsoft Excel for six variables relating to macro-level translation methods, broadly corresponding to House's (2016) 'complexity of translation' which includes the macro-level features : translation task variables (why? Who for?), situational variables (where? When?), translator variables (who?). These features are adjusted to fit the LDT context based on a pilot test with an initial subset of the data, and the information that is freely available on ELAR, to provide information to determine:

- The genres of texts that are selected to be translated, transcribed and glossed (House's (2016) Translation task variable).
- the choice of target language(s) (House's (2016) Translation-task variable and Situational variable)
- the choice of translator (House's (2016) Translator variable)

⁶ Several deposits contained files that had restricted access. Therefore, these files were excluded from the study.

The six variables: Genre of text, transcription present, translation present, glossing present, language(s) of translated texts and translator acknowledgement are presented below.

3.1.2.1. Genre of text

This variable tracks the text genres represented in the corpus, and is a necessary first step in order to determine which genres have been transcribed, translated and/or glossed. Each text was initially assigned a label denoting its genre type, as displayed in the ELAR deposit materials. Disparities in genre labels were noted between deposits, where some of the collections tend to simplify the genre descriptions, while other used more specific genre descriptions. For example, the Yaqay collection (Olsson, 2021) contains just 4 genre labels, and the text, *The Journeys of the Priests* is labelled as 'narrative', while the description states that the text provides a 'community history'. Conversely, the Chhitkul-Rakchham collection (Martinez, 2020) contains 7 genre labels, including a separate label for 'oral history'. This disparity reflects wider issues of genre analysis since it is often difficult to define what exactly genres are, and texts may belong to more than one (Pedersen 2011: 127; see Salffner, 2015 and Franjeh, 2019 for further discussion on genres in ELAR).

Therefore, the genres were simplified to fit the most general labels found in the corpus, so that each category was more widely represented. Therefore, the single-speaker genres, *narrative*, *description*, *monologue* and *oral history* were simplified to *narrative*; the multi-speaker genres, *conversation*, *functional language*, *interview* and *interactive discourse* were simplified to *Interactive Discourse*; Folktales and mythology were simplified to *Traditional Tales*; *songs*, *jokes*, *riddles* and *prayers* were categorised together, and finally, the mainly non-linguistic categories of *performance*, *ritual*, *dance*, *event*, *observational recording* and *public speech* were simplified to *Observational Recording*. *Consent*, *Procedural* and *Elicitation* genres remain unchanged due to the relatively higher number of texts and wider distribution across deposits. Therefore, each text in the research corpus was coded with one of the simplified genres. The simplified genres are shown in Table 4, with the number of texts and number of deposits in which they appear. There remains some disparity between the numbers of texts included in each genre, which is reflective of the reality and content of the deposits.

Table 4: Simplified Genres

	Number of texts	Number of deposits represented
Narrative	467	10
Procedural	47	8
Elicitation	100	7
Consent	77	4
Song, Joke, Riddle, Prayer	37	7
Interactive Discourse	249	10
Observational Recording	39	4
Traditional tales	72	3
Total	1088	

3.1.2.2. Presence of Transcription, Translation and glossing

These variables were coded on binary scales (YES/NO).

3.1.2.2.1. Transcription Present YES/NO

This variable was coded as YES when the audio(-visual) text was accompanied by a transcription text file, whether using phonetic transcription or another orthography.

3.1.2.2.2. Translation Present Yes/NO

This variable was coded as YES when the audio(-visual) text was accompanied by a translation text file.

3.1.2.2.3. Glossing Present Yes/No

This variable was coded as YES when the audio or audio-visual text was accompanied by a text file of grammatical glossing conveying the semantic or syntactic information associated with each lexical item or morpheme (see The Leipzig Glossing Rules, 2008).

3.1.2.3. Language(s) of Translated texts

Where texts were coded as YES for the presence of translation, further coding was added to indicate the language(s) of the translated texts. Some texts were coded with more than one of these languages, where multiple translations were present (A sample text is provided in Appendix 5). The TT languages are shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Languages of Translated Texts

English
French
Spanish
Mandarin
Bislama
Tok Pisin
Indonesian

3.1.2.4. Translator Acknowledgement YES/NO

This variable was coded as YES when there was explicit reference to the role of translator, and a name was given.

3.1.3. Limitations

As mentioned, the dynamic quality of ELAR collections means that the deposits used in this research may be modified, and it has been argued that such amendments may render any ‘third-party description’, such as this research, invalid if the original data is changed (Bird & Simons, 2013, p.567). However, the aim of this research is to provide a snapshot of how current translation practices impact the usefulness of LDT texts, at this moment in time.

Furthermore, the variables are not considered to be the complete set of macro-level variables relevant to LDT.

3.2. Study 2: Micro-level translation strategies in LDT

The second part of this research was conducted to identify the micro-level translation strategies used to render cultural terms in LDT and follows the Descriptive Translation Studies (DTS) method of empirical description of translation practices (Toury, 1995).

3.2.1. Data

This study analysed a subset of the translated texts identified in Study 1. A corpus was created containing texts with the following features:

- Transcription present-YES
- Translation present-YES
- Glossing present-YES
- Language of TT-English.

During tests on an initial subset, it was found that the presence of glossing allows for a richer analysis of the translation since it aids the identification of pairs of meaning in the ST and TT and it is not possible to reliably identify cultural terms or translation strategies between STs and TTs that are not glossed.

Four deposits were excluded since three do not include translated texts in English and one does not include glossing. Therefore, the corpus includes 16 texts from 6 deposits. A variety of text genres is included, in order to give the broadest possible picture of translation practices within the limits of the available data. The aim was to create a corpus which had a similar number of cultural terms extracted from each deposit so that the results were not skewed towards any particular deposit/researcher. Therefore, due to wide variation in text lengths, some deposits are represented by a greater number of texts than others, with each text containing between 1 and 211 cultural terms. Due to the limitations of the available texts, it was not possible to include exactly the same number of extracted cultural terms from each deposit. The features of the 16 texts are shown in Table 6, and a full biographical list of texts is included in Appendix 3.

Table 6: Features of corpus texts

Reference	Genre	Number of terms extracted
Mithun (Ozerov, 2018)	Narrative	4
Kubuyam saba (Dohler, 2019)	Narrative	10
Gunsaa (Martinez et al., 2020)	Description	40
A local dish called hot (Martinez et al., 2020)	Description	17
Shiv Bhakti's experience at school (Martinez et al., 2020)	Narrative	9
Collecting pine leaves in Rakccham (Martinez et al., 2020)	Description	7
The origins of Mata Devi (Martinez et al., 2020)	Narrative	25
A storyteller's memory (Perlin et al., 2018)	Narrative	211
The journeys of the priests (Olsson & Tamkoimu, 2021)	Narrative	36
Zauzou marriage (Li & Li, 2017)	Narrative	31
Raising pigs (Li & Li, 2017)	Description	6
Red wine (Li & Li, 2017)	Procedural	5
Repair pipe (Li & Li, 2017)	conversation	8
Making Zauzou shoes (Li & Li, 2017)	Procedural	1
Ghost festival (Li & Li, 2017)	Narrative	1
Transformation from a frog (Li & Li, 2017)	Folk tale	11
Total		422

3.2.2. Variables

3.2.2.1. Source-culture terms

First, the cultural terms were manually identified and extracted from the source texts along with their contextual sentences or phrases. Here, a cultural term is defined by its absence in the target culture, as a term where the referent is likely to be generally known in the SC, but

not by the anglophone TC audience (following Baker, 2008 and Saldanha, 2011, p.250)⁷. A total of 422 'triplets' (ST term + gloss + TT rendering) were identified. If a term appeared multiple times with the same TT rendering, it was only extracted once. However, where a ST term appeared multiple times with different TT renderings, each different rendering was extracted separately.

3.2.2.2. Cultural Domains

Many categorisations of culturally salient domains have been suggested in the literature. Therefore, it was necessary to conduct a pilot study of an initial subsection of the corpus in order to reveal the semantic domains that were represented by cultural terms in the STs. Thus, domains were modified to match the realities of the data, rather than making the data fit a pre-existing model. The six domains are Place, People, Food, , Measurements, Ecology, and Cultural Objects/Practices. These domains are based on domains reported in Pedersen, (2011); Cronin, (2017) and Katan & Taibi, (2021). Table 8 illustrates the domains and numbers of terms.

Table 7: Cultural Domains Represented in the research corpus

Domain	Number of terms
People	64
Place	194
Food	30
Cultural Objects/Practices	63
Ecology	29
Measurements	39
TOTAL	422

⁷ Pedersen's (2011) work uses the term, *monocultural terms*. However, due to the context of endangered language linguistic ecologies, where multilingualism is common, this research favours a broader definition that includes cultural entities that may be known across various cultures (i.e. not monocultural), but unknown to anglophone cultures.

3.2.2.2. Translation Strategies

The 422 cultural terms were then coded with one or more strategy based on Pedersen's (2011) taxonomy of translation strategies, as presented in Chapter 2, and reproduced in Table 9.

Table 8: Strategies for rendering cultural terms (based on Pedersen, 2011)

Strategy	Sub-strategies
Retention	
Specification	Addition Completion
Direct Translation	
Generalisation	Paraphrase Hypernym
Substitution	Cultural Situational Linguistic
Omission	
Official Equivalent	

An initial test on a subsection of the data revealed a sub-type of substitution that does not appear in Pedersen's (2011) existing taxonomy. This strategy involves substitution by a term from a language of wider communication and has been added to the taxonomy under the label, *linguistic substitution*. This strategy is illustrated in Example 1, where the ST term *ri* is glossed as *food* and appears in the TT as *dhindo (porridge)*. The term *dhindo* is from Nepali, a local language of wider communication.

Example 1

ST dangbo kalo **ri** ken yoli nalza

Gloss Long.ago era **food** stir if pot.small

TT Those pots were used to make as nalza to make **dhindo (porridge)**

Perlin2018,seke-perlin-0541.00:16:16.226⁸

3.2.3. Limitations

The corpus size is not large enough to fully reveal ‘norms’ in LDT, particularly since the data only represents 6 deposits – By contrast, Pedersen’s (2011) study surveys 906 ST terms, with 1887 TT renderings in two languages. Furthermore, the sample is not weighted so that each genre is proportionally represented, although efforts have been made to use a range of genres.

However, the aim is to provide a first snapshot of current practices in LDT practices, as carried out by a range of translators from a range of source languages and cultures in a range of contexts.

⁸ See Appendix 1 for guide to references of ELAR texts.

4. Results

4.1. Macro-level Methods

4.1.1. Transcription, Translation and Glossing

Of the 1088 Endangered Language source texts, 526 (48.3%) are transcribed, 528 (48.5%) are translated⁹ and 287 (26.3%) are glossed. The proportions of annotations vary between deposits, with standard deviations of 26.8 (transcription), 27.1 (translation) and 22.4 (glossing) (See Table 9). Figure 1 illustrates the variation, which ranges from the lowest level of annotation: no transcription, translation or glossing (Sanapana, Van Gysel, 2020) to the highest level of annotation: transcriptions and translations for all texts, and glossing for over half (57%) (Chhitkul-Rakchham, Martinez, 2020). Six deposits include more transcribed and translated texts than glossed texts. Just two deposits include transcription, translation and glossing for more than half of their texts.

Table 9: Percentage of transcription, translation and glossing by deposit

Deposit	Total texts	Transcribed		Translated		Glossed	
		Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Chhitkul-Rakchham	72	72	100	72	100	41	56.9
Gildipasi	105	84	80	84	80	0	0
Ahamb	216	128	59.2	128	59.2	128	59.2
Anal	99	57	57.5	57	57.5	1	1
Nam Trik	75	35	46.6	32	42.6	6	8
Yaqay	19	8	42	7	37	1	5
Zauzou	331	103	31.1	112	33.8	102	30.8
Bine	107	32	29.9	30	28	0	0
Seke	23	7	30.4	7	30.4	7	30.4
Sanapana	41	0	0	0	0	0	0
TOTAL	1088	526	48.3%	529	48.6%	286	26.3%

⁹ The disparity between transcription and translation can be accounted for by two texts that are not transcribed, but include a written summary in English. Therefore, the text is translated directly from audio SL – written TL.

Translation Studies MA Dissertation

Figure 1: Percentage of Transcription, Translation and Glossing by deposit.

4.1.2. Genre

There are more translated than glossed texts in all genres (Table 11). Narratives are most frequently translated (63.3%) and glossed (38.3%), followed by procedural texts (55.3% translated and 31.9% glossed). Notably, less than half of interactive texts (48.1%) are translated, and only 10 percent are glossed. Less than half of traditional tales are translated (47.2%), with only around 20 percent glossed. Elicitations display a higher proportion of glossing than other genres, with 46 percent of texts translated, and 36 percent glossed – the second highest rate of glossing. Songs, jokes, riddles and prayers are translated 40 percent of the time, and glossed in 32.4 percent of cases. The mainly non-linguistic *observational texts* are translated in 12.8 percent of cases and glossed in 7.6 percent of cases. *Consent* texts are never translated or glossed (See Table 10, Figure 2).

Translation Studies MA Dissertation

Table 10: Percentage of transcribed, translated and glossed texts by genre.

Genre	Translated		Glossed		Total texts
	Number	%	Number	%	
Narrative	283	60.5	179	38.3	467
Procedural texts	26	55.3	15	31.9	47
Interactive	120	48.1	27	10.8	249
Traditional Tales	34	47.2	15	20.8	72
Elicitation	46	46	35	36	100
Songs, jokes, riddles, prayers	15	40.5	12	32.4	37
Observational	5	12.8	3	7.6	39
Consent	0	0	0	0	77
Total	529	48.6%	286	26.3%	1088

Figure 2: Translation and Glossing by genre.

Translation Studies MA Dissertation

4.1.3. Languages of translated texts

Out of 529 TTs, 370 (69.9%) are provided in English, while 435 (82.2%) are provided in another local language of wider communication (See Table 11 for the figures for each deposit). The languages found in the corpus are: Bislama, Spanish, Tok Pisin, Mandarin, Hindi and Indonesian. Three deposits provide TTs only in English, while one deposit provides TTs only in a local language. Figure 3 provides a visual representation showing that more than half of the translated texts are provided in both English and another language.

Table 11: Percentage of TTs by language

Deposit	Total TTs	English		Local Language	
		Number	%	Number	%
Chhitkul-Rakchham	72	72	100	72	100
Gildipasi	84	84	100	84	100
Ahamb	128	7	5.4	128	100
Anal	57	57	100	0	0
Nam Trik	32	0	0	32	100
Yaqay	7	7	100	7	100
Zauzou	112	106	94.6	112	100
Bine	30	30	100	0	0
Seke	7	7	100	0	0
Sanapana	0	0	0	0	0
TOTAL	529	370	69.9%	435	82.2%

Figure 3: Languages of translated texts (%)

Translation Studies MA Dissertation

4.1.4. Translator acknowledgement

The corpus reveals a widespread lack of translator acknowledgement. Acknowledgement is given for only 146 (27.6 %) translated texts. Strikingly, as shown in Table 12, these translator acknowledgements account for just three deposits, and within these three deposits, the translator is not consistently named (71%, 52% and 21%, respectively). No information about translators or translation work was found in TTs in the remaining seven deposits.

Table 12: : Translator acknowledgement

Deposit	Number of texts	%
Ahamb	0	0
Anal	12	21%
Bine	0	0
Gildipasi	55	52%
Chhitkul-R	0	0
Nam Trik	0	0
Sanapana	0	0
Seke	0	0
Yaqay	0	0
Zauzou	79	71%
TOTAL	146	27.6%

Translation Studies MA Dissertation

4.2. Micro-level translation strategies used to render cultural terms.

Table 13: Translation strategies by domain

Strategies	People		Place		Food		Cultural Objects/Practices		Ecological		Measurements		TOTAL	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Retention	7	10.9	77	39.6	5	16.6	14	22.2	1	3.4	6	15.3	110	26.3
Specification	14	21.8	71	36.5	9	30	27	42.8	10	34.4	7	17.9	138	33
Direct Translation	19	29.6	1	0.5	5	16.6	0	0	6	20.6	15	38.4	46	11
Generalisation	19	29.6	0	0	3	10	12	19	5	17.2	0	0	39	9.3
Substitution	0	0	0	0	1	3.3	5	7.9	3	10.3	2	5.1	11	2.6
Omission	1	1.5	1	0.5	1	3.3	0	0	2	6.9	1	2.5	6	1.4
Official Equivalent	3	4.6	42	21.6	0	0	0	0	1	3.4	7	17.9	53	12.6
Combination	1	1.5	2	1	6	20	5	7.9	1	3.4	0	0	15	3.5
Total	64	15.3	194	46.4	30	7.1	63	15	29	6.9	39	9.3	418	100

4.2.1. Strategies

A total of 422 cultural term triplets (ST term + gloss + TT rendering) were extracted from the corpus, of which 4 were discounted as they could not be decoded (See Appendix 3). As shown in Table 13, source-oriented strategies (Retention, Specification and Direct Translation) account for 294 renderings (70.3%), while target-oriented strategies (i.e. Generalisation, Substitution, Omission) account for just 56 renderings (13.3%), with Official Equivalents accounting for 53 renderings (12.6%) and combinations of strategies accounting for 15 cases (3.5%). See Appendix 3 for samples of all strategies.

4.2.1.1. Retention

Retention is the second most frequent strategy in the corpus, accounting for 110 cultural terms (26.3 %) and is used in all domains. Proper Nouns are generally retained, comprising of 77 place names (39.6% of place terms) and 7 people's names.

4.2.1.2. Specification

Specification is the most frequently used strategy in the corpus, accounting for 33% of all renderings, across all domains. Specification by Addition accounts for the majority of cases (97.8%) with just 3 cases of Completion (2.2%) (See Appendix 3). Specification is by far the most used strategy in the *Cultural Items/Practices* domain (42.8% of renderings), most commonly for festivals, rituals, customs and games.

4.2.1.3. Direct Translation

Direct translation accounts for 46 renderings of cultural terms (11%) and is the most used strategy in the domains of *Measurements*, with 15 cases (38.4%), and *People* with 19 cases (29.6%), and relatively fewer cases in the other domains.

4.2.1.4. Generalisation

Generalisation accounts for 39 cultural term renderings (9.3%) and is the one of the most used strategies in the domain of *People*, with 19 cases (29.6%).

4.2.1.5. Substitution

Although Substitution only accounts for a total of 19 cases (4.5%), which includes 11 renderings (2.6%) as a single strategy, and a further 8 terms (1.9%) in combination with specification, this strategy illustrates an interesting finding, that is not included in Pedersen's (2011) taxonomy, which is substitution by a lexical item from a third language, termed Linguistic Substitution. Although the substitute lexical item may be a direct translation or generalisation, the common feature is that it is written in a third language, and is a term that is not already used in the TL. Linguistic Substitution (alone or combined) is

mostly used to render *Food*, with 7 terms (23.3%), and *cultural objects/practices*, with 10 cases (15.8%).

4.2.1.6. Omission

There are only 6 cases of Omission in the TTs (1.4%), and most of those cases are likely to be errors rather than intentional strategies. Therefore, Omission will not be discussed further.

4.2.1.7. Official Equivalent

There are 53 Official Equivalent renderings (12.6%), which mostly account for *Place* names - 42 cases (21.6%) and *Measurements* - 7 (17.9)

4.2.1.8. Combinations

Five combinations of strategies are found in the corpus, shown in Table 14.

Table 14: Combined Strategies

Strategies	N	%
Substitution + Specification	8	1.9
Direct Translation + Specification	4	0.9
Official Equivalent + Specification	1	0.2
Retention + Omission	1	0.2
Retention + Direct Translation	1	0.2
TOTAL	15	3.5

3.2.2. Strategies according to deposit

It is also revealing to consider the findings of Study 2 in terms of the deposits surveyed. This research highlights that different translation strategies are more dominant in different deposits. Table 15 shows that three deposits (Anal, Bine and Chhitkul-Rakchham) demonstrate a preference for Specification, one deposit (Yaqay) demonstrates a preference for Retention, one deposit (Seke) uses Retention and Specification in similar proportions and one deposit (Zauzou) includes more cases of Direct translation and Generalisation. So while there is an overall preference for Specification and Retention, there is variation between the deposits. This will be discussed further in the following chapter, and is represented in Figure 4.

Table 15: Translation strategies by deposit

Strategies	Anal		Bine		Chhitkul-R		Seke		Yaqay		Zauzou		TOTAL	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Retention	1	25	3	30	10	10.2	67	31.7	26	72.2	3	4.7	110	26.3
Specification	2	50	4	40	66	67.3	62	29.3	2	5.5	2	3.1	138	33
Direct Translation	0	0	0	0	2	2	16	7.5	0	0	28	44.4	46	11
Generalisation	0	0	1	10	1	1	21	9.9	1	2.7	15	23.8	39	9.3
Substitution	0	0	0	0	1	1	2	0.9	0	0	8	12.6	11	2.6
Omission	0	0	0	0	1	1	2	0.9	2	5.5	1	1.5	6	1.4
Official Equivalent	0	0	1	10	12	12.2	32	15.1	4	11.1	4	6.3	53	12.6
Combination	0	0	0	0	5	5.1	9	4.2	1	2.7	0	0	15	3.5
Unknown	1	25	1	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	3.1	4	0.9
TOTAL	4		10		98		211		36		63		422	100

Translation Studies MA Dissertation

Figure 4: Translation strategies by deposit (%)

5. Discussion

This chapter presents a discussion of the findings of this research, a first empirical investigation into micro- and macro-level strategies used in the translation of language documentation texts. First, the macro-level strategies are discussed and analysed in terms of the implications on the multi-purpose use of the TTs by potential audiences. Second, the micro-level strategies used to translate cultural terms are discussed and analysed in terms of implications on the multi-purpose use of the TTs by their potential audiences.

A text sample is provided in Appendix 5, while a sample of translated cultural terms is provided in Appendix 4.

5.1. Macro-level Translation decisions

5.1.1. Macro-Level Methods used in LDT

Four key macro-level translation areas are discussed: The choice to translate and/or gloss, which genres of texts to translate and/or gloss, the language chosen for the translated texts and who the translator is. This section will elaborate the findings and the resulting implications on how, and by whom, the TTs can be used, to determine whether current practices in LDT are producing texts that are truly 'multi-purpose', as advocated in the LD literature (e.g. Himmelmann, 2006).

5.1.1.1. The choice to translate and/or gloss

Far fewer texts are grammatically glossed, than are translated – 26.3% and 48.6%, respectively. This section examines the implications on how and by whom the LD translated and/or glossed texts can be used.

As mentioned in Chapter 2, many of the potential users of LD texts, including language teachers, community members and people from outside the community, are not fluent

speakers of the language (O'Shannesey *et al.*, 2019; Czaykowska-Higgins, 2009; Schwartz & Dobrin, 2016). This means that in order to access the texts, translation into appropriate language(s) is crucial. However, less than half of the texts in this research are translated, meaning that just over half of the texts are not accessible to anyone who does not speak the endangered SLs. Therefore, more than half of the endangered language texts surveyed are, in many cases, not suitable for use for the development of pedagogical materials from the texts, since language teachers are unable to search for and identify useful language (Underriner *et al.*, 2021). In addition, more than half of the texts are not suitable for use in wider academic contexts, since the ST is unlikely to be accessible to many researchers beyond the original project. Finally, this finding means that more than half of the endangered language communities' words are not able to be heard in more contexts, and that any information within those texts, including important ecological knowledge, is unlikely to be retrievable.

Furthermore, this research finds that glossing is also necessary in allowing the texts to be used for a variety of purposes. In the process of this research, which involved working with texts in 10 endangered languages that the researcher had no prior knowledge of, it was found that locating and isolating pairs of meaning from an endangered language ST and accompanying TT is often impossible or inaccurate without the presence of glossing, which provides a link between the ST and TT. For example, in Example 2, below, without the presence of the gloss, a non-SL speaker is able to access a general meaning of the sentence. However, this meaning is unclear due to the retention of the SL term *nalza*, and the difficulty in determining which elements of the ST correspond with which elements of the TT. This holds true in many cases of translation from endangered SLs to English, since the range of language families, and therefore, syntactic structures is varied, and there is no simple equivalence.

Example 2

ST	dangbo kalo ri ken yoli	nalza
gloss	long.ago era LOC food stir	pot.small
TT	those pots were used to make as nalza	

This means that for language learning purposes, someone working with a text that is accompanied by free translation could memorise whole phrases, but they would not be able to manipulate the constituent elements separately. When glossing is provided, users can determine the correspondences between the ST and the TT, meaning that they can gain a deeper understanding of the phrase, and manipulate and extract the constituent elements, thus allowing them to use the language. For example, language activist, Lindsay Marean, who is learning her heritage language, Potawatomi, reports that thanks to access to documentary texts, and analysing the meaning, 'we are developing a feel for how our first language speakers use our language, and we are gaining new insights into traditional Potawatomi ways of thinking' (Unerriner *et al.*, 2021, p.244). This shows the real impact that suitable texts have on successful language learning initiatives, which can lead to increased linguistic rights and social justice for the community, for current and future generations

Glossing is also a crucial element to enable wider academic use of LD texts, as it allows for linguistic analysis, as well as ensuring accountability and that research findings, as well as translations, are 'transparent' (Woodbury 2003, 2011), verifiable, replicable and/or reproducible. This is particularly important in the context of endangered language texts, since it is unlikely that the data will be able to be collected again (Gawne *et al.*, 2017, p158).

Only around a quarter (26.3%) of the texts surveyed provide both glossing and free translation, meaning that only this small proportion of texts could be described as 'multi-purpose', for developing language learning materials, or for academic, and wider use beyond the initial documentation project.

5.1.1.2. Genres of TTs

The choice of which genres of texts are translated and/or glossed also has implications on how and by whom TTs can be used.

As mentioned in Chapter 2, texts providing examples of ‘everyday language’ are most useful for language learning (Austin, 2021, p. 202; Underriner *et al*, 2021, p. 237) and it has been reported that many LD deposits do not contain suitable genres of texts (Sallabank & King, 2021, p.35).

For language learning purposes, the most useful, ‘everyday’, genres are likely to be interactive texts, including conversations, interviews and functional language, since these texts contain a wide variety of rich, communicative language. This research reveals that out of 249 interactive texts, only 27 (10.8%) are provided with both glossing and free translation, with 48.5% freely translated. This means that nearly 90 percent of the Interactive texts are not glossed and translated, and therefore cannot be described as multi-purpose since they are unlikely to be suitable for language learning, or wider use, both in the present and the future.

Narrative and elicitation are the genres that are most likely to be glossed and translated (38.3% and 36%, respectively). This could be for several reasons: Firstly, priority may be given to processing texts for the research interests of the initial project, accounting for the relatively higher rate of glossing for elicitions, which tend to be targeted to the researcher’s interests. Secondly, it has been suggested that single-speaker texts with a narrow range of vocabulary are less-challenging and time-consuming to translate and gloss, since there is less overlapping speech or unknown vocabulary items (Collins, 2021). However, the focus on elicitation and narrative does not represent natural, communicative language use, and is therefore less likely to be suited to language learning or wider use.

5.1.1.3. Choice of Language of TT

The choice of language to translate into also affects who can access the TTs. English is likely to be more accessible for academic use, since English dominates academia (Apter, 2013; Bennet, 2015). Conversely, local languages of wider communication are more likely to be accessible to the language community, since it is understood that minority languages are often displaced by local dominant languages (Skutnabb-Kangas, 2000). This research reveals

that more than half (52%) of the translated texts are provided in both English and a local dominant language, meaning that these texts are potentially accessible to a wide range of users – from both within the language communities and more widely. However, of the remaining half of TTs, 30% are provided only in a language of wider communication, while 18% are provided only in English. When we consider that, of the 1088 texts in the corpus, only 286 (26.3%) provide sufficient annotation to be described as ‘multi-purpose’ for their potential audiences, and then that only 52% of those texts are likely to be translated into both English and a language of wider communication, we are left with an estimated 49 texts (13.6%) that can be said to be truly ‘multi-purpose’ in terms of annotation provision and TT language(s).

However, it is noteworthy that all glossing is provided in English, meaning that in order to be able to analyse the texts linguistically, produce language learning materials and for verification/replication/reproduction purposes, at least a basic knowledge of English and/or how to read glossing is required. The corpus also reveals a lack of uniformity in how glossing is realised, adding to the challenges of understanding and decoding. This is evident in the examples below, taken from two different deposits. The glossing in (4) uses a combination of English words and ST words; while the glossing in (5) uses a combination of grammatical abbreviations and English words. The effect of this disparity means that different skills and competences are required in order to decode the meanings – arguably skills that require training in linguistics, or at least a basic knowledge of grammatical function abbreviations in order to understand that, for example, the abbreviation ‘CL’ refers to the word class, ‘classifier’.

Translation Studies MA Dissertation

Example 3

	Dish
ST	alu sabzi raŋ hot ta bǎ mǎ nimi a:ts
gloss	potato sabzi with chilte is very tasty happen/become
TT	Chilta is very tasty with alu sabzi

(Martinez et al.2020, TRD_cik04GD20181126.00:07:46.710)

Example 4

	Measurement
ST	de31 qong55 de55 ve13 nai33 a55si55 jin33 nga31 a31 u13 u13si13 jin33 nga33 a31 u13
Gloss	one CL.jar DEM.DIST CL TOP 20 MW.jin know NEG RES.successful 50 MW.jin know NEG RES.successful
TT	It's not known if a jar is 20 jin or 50 jin

Li & Li2017,YangLiZhong02.00:04:31.405

These idiosyncrasies may reflect the different academic backgrounds and research interests of the LD researchers. Although The Leipzig Glossing Rules set out standards for linguistics, to the best current knowledge, there has been no research or attempt to theorise glossing within theories of translation. This is an area of development that would greatly benefit the creation of 'multi purpose' LD texts.

5.1.1.4. Choice of Translator

The Macro-level decision of who translates a text has an impact on how and by whom the TT can be used. This research reveals that translator acknowledgement is given for just 27.6 percent of TTs, meaning that almost three quarters of the TTs make no reference to the translator. Therefore, it is not possible to determine any generalisable information about

the translators. Instead, this research supports reports in the LD literature regarding the lack of prestige given to the translation process within LD, that is evident from the lack of research on LDT within the field (as noted by Beier, 2015), thus rendering the labour of translation invisible.

However, the reality of the labour involved in annotating LD source texts by adding transcription, glossing and translation, has been estimated to take between 40 - 150 minutes for every minute of audio (Collins, 2016; Himmelmann, 2018, p.34), and anecdotal evidence provided by researchers indicates that the process often involves multiple actors (Collins, 2016). Therefore, erasing this labour from the final TT by not acknowledging translation work may have several important implications. Firstly, the cultures and ideologies of each of the participants in the translation process have an effect on the TT, meaning that TTs lacking acknowledgements are less accountable, verifiable and reproducible since neither the translators' sociolinguistic backgrounds, nor their personal translation styles, can be taken into consideration, thereby concealing 'the cultural and ideological positioning of the translator' (Baker, 2000).

Furthermore, rendering the labour of translation invisible, and therefore minimizing the agency of the translator(s), may have negative consequences in terms of fostering empowerment and revitalisation within the SL community, in addition to raising questions over (the lack of) endangered source language speakers' control over what, when and how texts might be translated into or out of their languages (Cronin 2003: 165-172).

5.2. Micro-Level Strategies

Following the previous discussion of Study 1 of this research, this section discusses Study 2, which surveys the micro-level strategies used to translate cultural terms in LDT texts with the aim of highlighting the impact of the strategies used on the TT audience's use of the texts.

Overall, so-called source-oriented strategies (Retention, Specification and Direct Translation) are used much more frequently than target-oriented strategies in the LDT

corpus, accounting for more than three-quarters of cultural term renderings. This is in line with the aims of LD, to bring the audience closer to the SL, and to bring the SL into other contexts and uses. However, while this binary distinction (source- vs target-oriented) gives a broad picture of strategies used, it does not show what the effect of these strategies might be on the potential TT audience(s). Therefore, this section aims to present a more nuanced understanding and analysis by examining specific translation strategies as used in cultural domains (Sections 5.2.1.-7), and as used by different translators (Section 5.2.8.).

5.2.1. Retention

Retention is the second most frequently used strategy, accounting for 26.3 % of all cultural term renderings. It is used in all domains, most commonly for rendering proper noun names of places or people. This is in line with previous TS findings, where proper nouns are reported to often be retained (e.g. Pedersen, 2011; Zarei & Norouzi, 2014, p.153).

Retention of proper nouns is argued to be a felicitous strategy since TT audience members are likely to be able to access and understand the referent, either through transcultural knowledge, familiarity with the source culture, or deictically (Nord, 2003, p183; Pedersen, 2011). Much preceding research has studied translation between languages with relatively small cultural distances, with some degree of familiarity, such as European languages. Thus, according to the EU style guide (2017, p.28), more and more people are now familiar with foreign place names, meaning that original SL names can be used without problem.

However, this Eurocentric perspective is more problematic in the case of LDT for several reasons. Firstly, in multilingual contexts, which are common in endangered language communities, it is not always clear what the original name of a place is, as the same place may have different names in different local languages. Secondly, due to the larger cultural distances, anglophone audience members are unlikely to be familiar with or able to access the referent of a retained proper noun, particularly place names. To illustrate, the Yaqay place name 'Qatan' is rendered in the TT by retention (see Example 2, Appendix 4). It is clear from the context that this term refers to the name of a place, but the significance, including cultural connotations, is not accessible in the TT, giving a limited, superficial understanding. This is further compounded by the lack of reference texts available in most endangered languages, meaning that the ST name is not printed on a map, dictionary or

online, so cannot be independently verified by the audience. Therefore, this research supports the argument that places that are not widely known outside of the SC, might need to be explained further than Retention allows (Särkkä, 2007).

Retention is also used to render food, cultural objects and practices with similar effects on the TT audience. For example, the Seke term, 'shapro' is retained in the TT, 'we danced shapro' (Ex5, Appendix4), and the Chhitkul-Rakchham term, 'alu sabzi' is retained in the TT, 'alu sabzi is very tasty with salad'. In both TT examples, a general scope of meaning can be understood from the context, that 'shapro' is a kind of dance, and 'alu sabzi' is a kind of food. However, it is not possible for anglophone audience members to access the specific referent, along with associated connotational meanings, without existing knowledge of the SC.

Interestingly, 'alu sabzi' appears to have been borrowed into the Chhitkul-Rackchham lexicon from Hindi, a local dominant language, thereby illustrating a common feature of multilingual contexts where translanguaging – the fluid use of more than one language - is common (Garcia & Wei, 2014; Baynham & King Lee, 2019). Furthermore, in the text corpus, borrowed lexical items tend to be retained, as illustrated in the domain of measurements. For example, the Zauzou ST includes the Mandarin borrowing, 'jin' which is retained in the TT: '...a jar is 20 jin or 50 jin' (Ex3, Appendix4).

According to previous research (Pedersen, 2011; Baker, 2018) retention of SL lexis in the TT brings the audience closer to the SL and attempts to introduce the SL into wider contexts. However, if the term is not familiar to anglophone audience members and if the meaning cannot be accessed from the text, or through reference materials, it can be argued that the audience is not really coming closer to the SL, since the retained term acts as no more than a general place-holder in the TT, indicating the function of the word, but offering no guidance as to the denotational nor connotational meaning. Therefore, following Cronin's argument that people can only pay meaningful attention to what they can understand (2017, p21), it is likely that many potential users of the text will skip past the retained lexis, since they cannot understand it. Thus, while retention may be a felicitous strategy in

allowing local community members to access the texts¹⁰, it clearly does not foster understanding among anglophone users, and therefore cannot be said to render the TTs 'multi-purpose'.

5.2.2. Specification

Specification is the most frequently used strategy for rendering cultural terms and is used in all domains in the corpus. This supports Pedersen's (2011) findings that Specification is generally used to render terms that are very monocultural and important to the text, since many of the SL terms found in the corpus are highly culture-specific to the source language and likely to be unfamiliar to the anglophone TT audience due to the large cultural distance between SCs and the anglophone TC. Furthermore, the current research findings differ from Pedersen's study in that specification was found to be used much less frequently in the Nordic-anglo translation context (Pedersen identifies specification for only around 5% of renderings), which may be indicative of the differing cultural distances.

A common finding in the data is the use of specification with a hypernym. For example, The Seke culture-specific kinship term, 'nyezangza' is rendered in the TT through specification as 'nyezang (family allies)' (Ex11, Appendix 4), thereby retaining the SL lexical item in addition to adding a TL hypernym. However, the anglophone audience cannot access the full meaning of the term since 'family ally' does not correspond to an equivalent relationship in the anglophone TC. Therefore, it is not clear which relationships 'nyezang' defines, and the TT audience may wonder whether it refers to friends, relations, colleagues, or others. Furthermore, the hypernym, 'allies', has connotations of conflict in English and it is not clear whether this connotation is shared by the SL term, or whether a more appropriate term could have been employed, such as, 'family friends'. In addition, the Yaqay place name, 'ure gome', is rendered in the TT with the Retention of the ST term, in addition to the hypernym, 'place name' (Example 13, Appendix 4). As previously mentioned, understanding that the term functions as a place name can be gained through context, meaning that this hypernym

¹⁰ Further research is required to reveal how retention affects the TTs that are produced in local dominant languages, and to determine whether this strategy hinders understanding by local community users.

is redundant and adds no further connotational information, therefore not facilitating any more access to the referent than in cases of retention.

The corpus data also reveals examples of specification using paraphrases, such as the Seke term, 'taksta', which is rendered in the TT as, 'taksta (game of tiger and goats)' (Ex22, Appendix 4); and examples of specification using longer sentences, making the term much more accessible to anglophone audience members, such as the Chhitkal-Rakchham rendering of the cultural practice, 'gunsa:', which is rendered in the TT by retention of the ST word, and an additional sentence, formatted as a translator's note, 'Gunsa: refers to is a process or tradition in the whole Kinnaur District whereby people 'migrate' to warmer locations during winter season.' (Ex21, Appendix 4). This

Therefore, the current research illustrates that specification is used in a variety of different ways, including the use of hypernyms, paraphrases and explanatory sentences, thereby supporting previous arguments that the decision taken by translators over what extra information to include in the TT is not objective, rather it depends on what they consider to be implicit and/or presupposed in the ST referent (Saldanha, 2008¹¹), and therefore will differ from translator to translator. Arguably, this variation also reflects the lack of training in LDT, leading LD translators to use strategies that may exhibit increased redundancy, rather than informativeness, as shown in the examples above. Furthermore, the effect of the strategy is dependent on the real-world knowledge of the TT audience (Saldanha, 2008, p.26-28), which presents an issue in the case of multi-purpose texts, where different audiences have different knowledge and experiences. For example, community members wishing to use the texts for language learning and language revitalisation purposes may be able to access culturally salient referents from hypernyms or paraphrases, while the wider audience is only likely to be able to understand the function of the lexical item, without understanding its semantic meaning. Therefore, the wider audience is likely to require more intervention by way of translation strategies in order to access the referent in any meaningful way.

¹¹ Saldanha's research is based on the related notion of 'explicitation' as conceptualised by Vinay & Darbelnet, 1958.

5.2.3. Direct Translation

Direct translation is the fourth most common strategy in the corpus data, and tends to be used in transcultural cases, where the referent is likely to be known within both the SC and TC, in the domains of kinship, ecology and food. Furthermore, direct translation is the most commonly used strategy for rendering measurements.

Transcultural kinship terms – relationships that are found in both source and target cultures – are generally directly translated. This is illustrated by terms such as, the Zauzou term ‘i33 bei55’, which is rendered as ‘Aunties’ (Ex23, Appendix 4) or the Seke ‘za’ which is rendered as ‘son’ (Ex27, Appendix 4), where the referent is accessible to both ST and TT audiences. Therefore, this research supports previous findings that direct translation is an effective strategy for transcultural terms, since they do not cause translation problems, and the referent can be accessed by both ST and TT audiences (e.g. Pedersen, 2011; Baker, 2018; Katan & Taibi, 2021).

Direct translation is also commonly used in the text corpus to render measurements, which is contrary to previous research that notes that measurements tend to be translated using official equivalents (Pedersen 2011; Epstein, 2009). For example, the Zauzou phrase ‘i35 na53 ei35 bang35’ is rendered in the TT as ‘take two bowls of wine’ (Ex24, Appendix 4) and the Seke phrase ‘Dadu kanang kanang nyo pungna’, is rendered in the TT as ‘they put two spatula's worth of milk’ (Ex25, Appendix 4).

In these cases, it does not seem that the ST and TT lexical items identify the same referent, allowing access to both the ST audience and TT audience. For example, the Zauzou rendering above remains somewhat ambiguous to the TT audience, since a bowl-based measurement system is not commonly used in the anglophone TC. Therefore, the target audience is likely to be left wondering what kind of bowls are being referred to, and unable to understand exactly what quantity of wine is being discussed, whereas SC members would be likely to understand the connotational meanings of the measurement, including the quantity. This strategy brings an interesting dimension to the TT, as it brings the audience closer to the ST and SC, and demonstrates different ways of conceptualising measurements.

Translation Studies MA Dissertation

However, the text is arguably not 'multi-purpose', since for language learning, cultural interest and academic analysis, potential users may wish to be able to understand the exact measurements.

5.2.4. Generalisation

The fifth most common strategy, generalisation, is particularly used to render culture-specific kinship terms, and cultural objects/practices.

For example, the Bine term, 'kege', is glossed as 'same sized brother' but is Generalised in the TT with the hypernym, 'brother', thus erasing part of the ST meaning (Ex28, Appendix 4). The use of the more general hypernym, with larger scope of reference, in the TT means that the TT audience cannot access the specific referent of the ST, rather, as with the previously mentioned cases of retention and specification by hypernym, the TT audience is able to access the function of the lexical item, but not its full semantic meaning.

A further disadvantage of generalisation is that, in contrast to the source-oriented strategies, it is not necessarily clear to the TT audience that the referent a) is specific to the SC and b) that the connotative and denotative meanings communicated in the TT are different to those communicated in the ST. This erasure of meaning could pose problems for language learners or other potential users of the TT. Whilst this loss of meaning is unlikely to hinder the TT audience's global understanding of the text, in the context of endangered languages where there exist power asymmetries between the endangered SL and global TL, it could be argued that erasing some of the meaning of the ST is not ethical practice.

5.2.5. Linguistic Substitution

Linguistic substitution involves using a lexical item from a local language of wider communication in the TT. For example, the Chhitkal-Rakchham dish 'hot' is rendered as 'chilta' in the TT (Ex9, Appendix 4). Although not a trans-cultural term and unlikely to be known by TT audience members outside of the local community, an internet search reveals

'chilta' to be food found throughout the region of Himachal Pradesh, where Chhitkal is spoken, meaning that any interested TT audience members are able to access the meaning through texts, such as an internet search¹². Linguistic substitution is often used in combination with specification. For example, the Seke food term, 'zima' is rendered in the TT with a Nepali¹³ term + English hypernym: 'zimbu (wild herb)' (Ex7, Appendix 4). Linguistic Substitution by a language of wider communication renders the referent more accessible to the TT audience, since the dominant local culture is likely to be more well-known trans-globally, and the lexis is more likely to be found in texts such as dictionaries/web searches. Furthermore, the addition of the hypernym 'wild herb' allows the TT audience to access the general scope of reference. However, the TT audience is still unlikely to really gain a sense of the connotative meaning including the 'social setting, cultural background, situation in time (past, present, future), religious or folk beliefs and relationship to the erotic or the aesthetic', which Cronin (2017, p.162) has argued is the role of a translator of food terms.

Furthermore, the substitution of the SL term for a dominant language appears to be symbolic of endangered language oppression, since the endangered language term is erased and replaced by the dominant language. In fact, it has been argued that substitution of ingredients in food writing, and resulting erasure of the SL and SC, changes the recipes more than a translation warrants (Epstein, 2015).

Furthermore, since this substitution is not made explicit to the TT audience, TT users may assume that the 'foreign' word is retained from the SC, leading to misunderstandings and exoticism of the text (see Shamma, 2005). Therefore, this strategy is interesting in terms of demonstrating the complexities of language and translanguaging (Garcia & Wei, 2014; Baynham & King Lee, 2019) in multi-lingual communities. However, it does not necessarily support the use of the TTs as multi-purpose materials, since it does not bring the global audience closer to the SL and could cause confusion for anyone attempting to use the text for language learning purposes.

¹² <https://blessingsonthenet.com/travel-india/destination/article/id/952/tour/id/396/cusine-in-kinnaur>

¹³ Accessible via Internet search. E.g. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Jimbu>

5.2.6. Official Equivalent

The cases of rendering by the use of official equivalents that occur in the corpus data, are found in the domains of place and measurements. Geographical names are defined as official equivalents when the TT rendering is a different lexical item to the ST, and can be found on a map. The use of exonyms has been reported as a common feature of place name translation (Nord, 2003, p.184; Pedersen, 2011), where geographical names have specific forms in other languages that are not used in the local language. However, in multilingual contexts, a geographical location may be known by multiple names, within the local area. This is illustrated in the rendering of the Chhitkul-Rakchham name, 'koelaso', which is rendered in the TT as, 'Mount Kailash'(ex38, Appendix 4). It seems that the English term is derived from the Sanskrit name, Kailasa, while the mountain is known by 'Gang Rinpoche' in Tibetan, the national language of Tibet where the mountain is located, and 'Gang Tise', in a Zhuang-Zhuang, a minority language of Tibet, in addition to the term, 'koelaso', found in the research data, which is the name used by the Chhitkul-Rakchham community in India. This indicates the complex nature of issues of ownership of geographical places, and, therefore, the complexity surrounding the notion of an original name. This strategy has the advantage of not requiring increased labour or intervention on the part of the translator, assuming the 'official' name is readily available, while providing a point of reference for TT audience members to discover more information. This rendering allows the audience to access the referent through their own encyclopaedic knowledge or through other texts, e.g. an internet search. However, as with the use of linguistic substitution, confusion could arise among TT audience members if they assume that the foreign term is a retained SL lexical item. Furthermore, many of the places mentioned in LD texts do not have official Anglophone names and thus, this strategy is not available to them, thereby supporting Pedersen's (2011) finding that Official Equivalents are not commonly used to render cultural terms, since source-culture terms are, by definition, not generally known in the TC.

5.2.8. Strategies by Deposit: The effect of the translator

The previous sections have demonstrated some tentative trends in the choice of strategies for translating cultural references in language documentation texts. However, it is also important to consider the choice of strategies used by individual translators or in individual ELAR deposits. While three deposits (Anal, Bine and Chhitkul-R) demonstrate a preference for Specification, one deposit (Yaqay) demonstrates a preference for Retention, one deposit (Seke) uses Retention and Specification in similar proportions and one deposit (Zauzou) includes more cases of Direct translation and Generalisation. Thus, the findings discussed above are likely to be influenced by the individual translators' styles, or 'thumbprints' (Baker, 2000, p.245), which are marked by subtle linguistic habits which the translator may not be conscious of (Baker, 2000, p.246).

For example, The Zauzou deposit (Li, 2017) differs substantially from the other deposits in that Direct Translation is used more than any other strategy, while the other include more cases of retention and specification. Therefore, since the Zauzou texts contain many measurement terms, direct translation is the found to be the most commonly used strategy for rendering measurements in the corpus data, even though this is not represented in the other deposits, which contain fewer measurement terms. Whether this is due to conscious or subconscious preferences or ideologies of the translator, lack of equivalence, the structure of the SL, or other factors is complicated to determine, and beyond the scope of this research. However, it is clear that the findings of the corpus data represent a snapshot of how LD translation of cultural terms is currently practiced, and should not be considered as translation norms.

As noted by Baker (2000, p258), the choice of translation strategies can tell us about the 'cultural and ideological positioning of the translator', but in order to determine a meaningful explanation as to why certain strategies have been chosen, it is necessary to triangulate the texts with extralinguistic, sociolinguistic information about the translator – something that this research has found to be lacking in LDT. Thus, emphasising the importance of raising the profile of translation and translator agency within the field of Language Documentation.

6. Conclusion

- 6.1. What does the investigation into translation of cultural terms reveal about macro- and micro-level strategies in LDT?

It is not possible to reach a definitive conclusion on the strategies used in LDT, or the impact these strategies have on how and by whom TTs are able to be used, given the limitations of this study. However, this research reveals several trends and key observations on how macro- and micro-level strategies are used in LDT, as found in the research corpus. The theorisation of translation as part of language documentation cannot be provided by a single piece of research, rather it is important that the field of LD engages in research and debate in this area. This dissertation aims to provide some evidence that can contribute to this under-researched area.

Bearing in mind the limitations, this research has demonstrated that decisions regarding which texts to leave untranslated, which texts to gloss and translate, which languages to translate into and who should translate them have an important impact on how, and by whom, TTs can be used. At the macro-level, there appears to be a lack of TTs that are suitable for use in community, academic or wider world contexts, beyond the initial research project. Furthermore, the lack of acknowledgement of translation labour suggests that translation is seen to be a low-prestige activity, and that LD researchers are unaware of the agency that they possess as translators or facilitators of translation. TTs could be rendered more useful to language communities as well as wider academic use by providing a greater proportion of translated and glossed texts, as well as ensuring that glossing and translation is provided for those genres that are most useful for revitalisation purposes – e.g. communicative everyday language.

At the micro-level, this research suggests that translators select a variety of strategies for translating cultural terms, however the resulting TT lexical items often bring increased redundancy to the TT audience, rather than increased informativeness. Therefore, few

cultural term renderings in the corpus data allow the TT audience to access the semantic meaning of the ST referent, beyond a shallow understanding.

Therefore, it seems that desire to remain faithful to the SL, in addition to lack of translator training may account for the lack of well-targeted, felicitous translation intervention, such as using redundant hypernyms, or directly translating culture-specific notions, such as culture-specific ways of conceptualising measurements. Furthermore, strategies that have been reported to be felicitous in Eurocentric contexts, such as retention, have been found to be more problematic in LDT, where the cultural distance is greater. Clearly, greater cultural distance requires greater intervention – illustrated by the high frequency of specification in the corpus data, while studies on translation in European contexts have found specification to be used more rarely (Pedersen, 2011, p.158).

These issues are likely to have an impact on how, and by whom the English TTs are used, by hindering global TT audience members' (both academic and other) access to invaluable indigenous knowledge, including cultural and ecological knowledge, which could be particularly important in light of the climate crisis (Stibbe, 2015; Cronin, 2017), in addition to hindering verification, replication and/or reproduction of any findings (Olalla-Soler 2020, reproduction Gawne et al. 2017, also cite Berez-Kroeker et al, 2017). Therefore, at least in terms of the English TTs, current practices for rendering cultural terms are generally not suitable for multi-purpose use.

Therefore, it seems that providing workshops or training on translation strategies to language documentation researchers could help to improve the translation output in terms of producing multi-purpose, lasting texts. This research suggests that it is necessary to identify translation strategies that can be used successfully in LDT, that are likely to differ from those used in Eurocentric contexts. For example, the use of full-sentence translator notes, used frequently in the Chhitkul-Rakchham deposit (Martinez, 2020) is generally felicitous, while the use of specification by hypernym generally causes increased redundancy in the TT, illustrating the need for more translation intervention in cases of greater cultural distance. As Cronin, (2017, p.20) points out,

“One of the paradoxes of untranslatability, of course, is that you need more translation not less. You have to try harder to understand what the other is saying, devote more resources to the effort and value successful translation all the more when it is achieved, precisely because it is so difficult.”

Furthermore, an increase in translator agency within the field of LD could be built through translator training, with translation exploited as a tool for meeting goals of language justice, and wider social justice issues. There is productive current research and discussion on the topics of translation training in crisis and emergency contexts (e.g. Federici et al., 2019; Cadwell et al. 2019) Community translation (Taibi, 2017), and minority language translator, which could be used as a basis for developing translation training within the field of Language Documentation. More research is required to determine how the crisis of language endangerment fits in with other areas of crisis translation.

6.2. Limitations of the research and areas of further study

The major limitation of this research is that it only surveys the English TTs associated with the endangered language STs, while many of the texts also include TTs in other, locally dominant languages. Therefore, research is required on the TTs rendered in other languages to provide a better picture of how micro-level translation strategies are used, and in particular, to reveal how these decisions affect use within the local community.

Furthermore, as mentioned above, the translator is conspicuously absent from the corpus data, meaning that the findings cannot be triangulated with extralinguistic information about translators, or their decision-making processes. Therefore, extra-textual research is required to discover who is translating LD texts, in addition to experimental methods to reveal the processes involved.

References

- Apter, E. (2013). *Against world literature: On the politics of untranslatability*. Verso.
- Austin, P. K. (2010). Current issues in language documentation. *Language Documentation and Description*, 7, 12–33. <http://www.elpublishing.org/PID/080>
- Austin, P. K. (2013). Language documentation and meta-documentation. In M. Jones & S. Ogilvie (Eds.) *Keeping languages alive: Documentation, pedagogy and revitalization*, (pp. 3-15). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781139245890.003>
- Austin, P. (2016). Language Documentation 20 Years On. In Filipovic, L. & Putz, M. (Eds.), *Endangered Languages and Languages in Danger: Issues of ecology, policy and human rights* (pp. 147-170). John Benjamins. <https://doi.org/10.1075/impact.42>
-
- Austin, P. K. (2017). Language documentation and legacy text materials. *Asian and African Languages and Linguistics* 11, 23-44. <http://hdl.handle.net/10108/89205>
- Austin, P. K. (2021). Language documentation and language revitalization. In J. Sallabank & J. Olko (Eds.), *Revitalizing endangered languages: a practical guide* (pp. 199- 219). <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108641142.014>
- Baker, M. (2000). Towards a Methodology for Investigating the Style of a Literary Translator. *Target*, 12(2), 241-266. <https://doi.org/10.1075/target.12.2.04bak>
- Baker, M. (2013). Translation as an alternative space for political action. *Social Movement Studies: Journal of Social, Cultural and Political Protest*, 12(1), 23-47. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14742837.2012.685624>
- Baker, M. (2018). *In other words: A coursebook on translation*. Taylor & Francis. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315619187>
- Bassnett, S & Johnston, D. (2019). The outward turn in translation studies. *The Translator*, 25(3), 181-188. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13556509.2019.1701228>
- Bassnett, S., & Lefevere, A. (1990). *Translation, History and Culture*. Printer Publishers.
- Baynham, M & King Lee, T. (2019) *Translation and translanguaging*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315158877>
- Beier, C. (2015, 23 April) *Text translation in the context of endangered language documentation: The case of Iquito* [Conference presentation]. Fieldwork Forum, Department of Linguistics, University of California, Berkeley. http://www.cabeceras.org/beier_translation_fforum_20150423.pdf

- Bennett, K. (2007). Epistemicide! The tale of a predatory discourse. *The Translator*, 13:2, 151 - 169, <https://doi.org/10.1080/13556509.2007.10799236>
- Berez-Kroeker, A. L., Gawne, L., Smythe Kung, S., Kelly, B. F., Heston, T., Holton, G., Pulsifer, P., Beaver, D. I., Chelliah, S., Dubinsky, S., Meier, R. T., Thieberger, N., Rice, K. & Woodbury, A. C. (2017). Reproducible research in linguistics: A position statement on data citation and attribution in our field. *Linguistics* 56(1), 1-18.
- Bird, S. & Simons, G. (2003). Seven Dimensions of Portability for Language Documentation and Description. *Language*, 79(3), 557–582. <https://doi.org/10.1353/lan.2003.0149>
- Blum-Kulker, S. (1986). Shifts of Cohesion and Coherence in Translation. In J. House & S. Blum-Kulka (Eds.), *Interlingual and Intercultural Communication: Dis-course and Cognition in Translation and Second Language Acquisition*. Narr, (pp. 17- 35).
- Cadwell, P., Bollig, C., & Ried, J. (2019). Management and Training of Linguistic Volunteers: A Case Study of Translation at Cochrane Germany. In F. M. Federici & S. O'Brien (Eds.), *Translation in Cascading Crises*, Routledge, (pp. 152–173).
- Cámara-Leret, R. & Bascompte, J. (2021). Language extinction triggers the loss of unique medicinal knowledge. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences Jun 2021*, 118(24). <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2103683118>
- Chesterman, A. (1997). *Memes of translation: the spread of ideas in translation theory*. John Benjamins. <https://doi.org/10.1075/btl.22>
- Collins, C. (2019, November 16). Rate of transcription in syntactic fieldwork. *Ordinary Working Grammarian*. <http://ordinaryworkinggrammarian.blogspot.com/2019/11/rate-of-transcription-in-syntactic.html#more>
- Cope, L. & Penfield, S. (2011). Applied linguist needed: cross-disciplinary networking for revitalization and education in endangered language contexts. *Language and Education*, 25(4), 267-271. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09500782.2011.577217>
- Czaykowska-Higgins, E. (2009). Research models, community engagement, and linguistic fieldwork: Reflections on working within Canadian indigenous communities. *Language Documentation & Conservation*, 3(1), 15-50. <http://hdl.handle.net/10125/4423>
- Cronin, M. (2003). *Translation and globalization*. Routledge.
- Cronin, M. (2006). *Translation and identity*. Routledge.
- Cronin, M. (2017). *Eco-Translation Translation and Ecology in the Age of the Anthropocene*. Routledge.

- Cronin, M. (2020). Minority. In Baker, M. & Saldanha, G. (Eds.), *Routledge Encyclopedia of Translation Studies* (pp. 334-338). Routledge.
- Cronin, M. & Delgado Luchner, C. (2021). Escaping the invisibility trap. *Interpreting and Society*, 1(1), 91-101. <https://doi.org/10.1177/27523810211033684>
- Dobrin, L., Austin, P. K., Nathan, D. (2009). Dying to be counted: the commodification of endangered languages in documentary linguistics. *Language Documentation and Description*, 6, 37-52. <http://www.elpublishing.org/PID/070>
- De Korne, H. & Leonard, W. H. (2017). Reclaiming languages: Contesting and decolonising 'language endangerment' from the ground up. *Language Documentation and Description*, 14, 5-14. <http://www.elpublishing.org/PID/149>
- Epstein, B. J. (2009). What's cooking? Translating food. *Translation Journal*, 13(3). <https://translationjournal.net/journal/49cooking.htm>.
- EU. (2016). *English style guide: A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission, Eighth edition*. https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/styleguide_english_dgt_en.pdf
- Evans, N. & Sasse, H-J. (2007). Searching for meaning in the Library of Babel: Field semantics and problems of digital archiving. *Language documentation and description*, 4, 58-99. <http://www.elpublishing.org/PID/050>
- Federici, F. M., O'Hagan, M, O'Brien, S, & Cadwell, P. (2019). Crisis Translation Training Challenges Arising from New Contexts of Translation. *Cultus: The Journal of Intercultural Mediation and Communication*, 12, 246–279. https://www.cultusjournal.com/files/Archives/Cultus_2019_12_013_Federici_et-al.pdf
- Fishman, J. A. (1991). *Reversing Language Shift*. Multilingual Matters.
- Fishman, J. A. (2001). *Can endangered languages be saved?* Multilingual Matters.
- Florin, S. (1993). Realis in translation. In P. Zlateva (Ed.), *Translation as Social Action. Russian and Bulgarian Perspectives*, (pp. 122-128). Routledge.
- Franjeh, M. (2019). The languages of northern Ambrym, Vanuatu: A guide to the deposited materials in ELAR. *Language Documentation & Conservation*, 13, 83-111. <http://hdl.handle.net/10125/24849>
- García, O. and Wei, L. (2014). *Translanguaging: Language, Bilingualism and Education*. Palgrave Macmillan. <https://doi.org/10.1057/9781137385765>
- Gawne, L., Kelly, B. F., Berez- Kroecker, A. L. & Heston, T. (2017). Putting practice into words: The state of data and methods transparency in grammatical descriptions. *Language Documentation & Conservation*, 11, 157-189. <http://hdl.handle.net/10125/24731>

- Grenoble, L. A. & Whaley, L. J. (2006). *Saving Languages: An Introduction to Language Revitalization*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511615931>
- Grenoble, L. A. (2010). Language documentation and field linguistics: The state of the field. In L. A. Grenoble & N. L. Furbee (Eds.), *Language documentation: practice and values*, (pp. 289–309). John Benjamins. <https://doi.org/10.1075/z.158.28gre>
- Grenoble, L. A. & Furbee, N. L. (Eds.). (2010). *Language documentation: Practices and values*. John Benjamins. <https://doi.org/10.1075/z.158>
- Grenoble, L. A. (2013). Unanswered questions in language documentation and revitalization: New directions for research and action. In E. Mihás, B. Perley, G. Rei-Doval, & K. Wheatley, (Eds.), *Responses to language endangerment: In honor of Mickey Noonan. New directions in Language Documentation and Language Revitalization*, (pp. 43-57). John Benjamins. <https://doi.org/10.1075/slcs.142.03gre>
- Hale, K., Krauss, M., Watahomigie, L., Yamamoto, A., Craig, C., Jeanne, L. & England, N. (1992). Endangered Languages. *Language*, 68, 1-42. [10.1353/lan.1992.0052](https://doi.org/10.1353/lan.1992.0052)
- Hale, S. & Liddicoat, A. (2015). The meaning of accuracy and culture, and the rise of the machine in interpreting and translation. A conversation between Sandra Hale and Anthony Liddicoat. *Cultus: The Journal of Intercultural Mediation and Communication*, 8, 14-26. <http://wrap.warwick.ac.uk/86141>
- Hall, E., T., (1990). *The silent language*. Doubleday. (Original work published 1959).
- Hatim, B. & Mason, I. (1990). *Discourse and the translator*. Routledge.
- Hermans, T. (1988). On translating proper names, with reference to De Witte and Max Havelaar. In M. Wintle (Ed.), *Modern Dutch Studies: Essays in honour of Peter King*, (pp. 11-24).
- Hervey, S. G. J. & Higgins, I. (1992). *Thinking translation: A course in translation method, French-English*. Routledge.
- Himmelman, N. P. (1998). Documentary and descriptive linguistics. *Linguistics*, 36, 161–195. <https://doi.org/10.1515/ling.1998.36.1.161>
- Himmelman, N. P. (2006). Language documentation: What is it and what is it good for? In J. Gippert, N. P. Himmelman, & U. Mosel (Eds.), *Essentials of language documentation*, (pp. 1–30). Mouton de Gruyter. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110197730>
- Himmelman, N. P. (2018). Meeting the transcription challenge. In B. McDonnell, A. Berez-Kroeker and G. Holton, (Eds.), *Reflections on language Documentation 20 years after Himmelman 1998. Language Documentation & Conservation Special Publication 15*, 33-40. <http://hdl.handle.net/10125/24806>

- Hinton, L., & Hale, K. (Eds.). (2001) *The green book of language revitalization in practice*. Academic Press.
- Hinton, L. (2011). Revitalization of endangered languages. In P. K. Austin & J. Sallabank (Eds.) *The Cambridge handbook of endangered languages*. Cambridge University Press. (pp.291 - 311)
<https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511975981>
- Hofstede, G. (1991). *Cultures and organizations: Software of the mind*. McGraw-Hill.
- Hornberger, N. H. (2010). Language Shift and Language Revitalization. In R. B. Kaplan, (Ed.) *The Oxford Handbook of Applied Linguistics (2 ed.)*. Oxford University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780195384253.013.0028>
- House, J. (2016). *Translation as Communication across Languages and Cultures*. Taylor & Francis.
- Hu, G. and Tao, Y. (2016). Eco-Translatology: A New Paradigm of Eco-translation. *Schools of Translation Studies: With Reference to the School of Eco-Translatology*, Macao Polytechnic Institute. http://cms.ewha.ac.kr/user/erits/download/review_6/6.pdf
- Inghilleri, M. (2008). The ethical task of the translator in the geo-political arena: From Iraq to Guantanamo Bay. *Translation Studies*, 1(2), 212-223.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/14781700802113556>
- Jakobsen, R. (2013). On linguistic aspects of translation. In R. A. Brower (Ed.) *On Translation*, (pp. 232-239). Harvard University Press. <https://doi.org/10.4159/harvard.9780674731615>
(Original work published 1959)
- Katan, D. and Taibi, M. (2021). *Translating cultures: An introduction for translators, interpreters and mediators*. Routledge.
- Kwiecinski, P. (2001). *Disturbing strangeness: Foreignisation and domestication in translation procedures in the context of cultural asymmetry*. Wydawnictwo Edytor.
- Lee, V. (2017). Cultural change and cultural mediation in the translation of culture-specific lexis. In O. I. Seel (Ed.), *Redefining Translation and Interpretation in Cultural Evolution*, (pp. 104 – 120). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-5225-2832-6.ch006>
-
- Leppihalme, R. (2001). Translation strategies for realia. In P. Kukkonen & R. Hartama-Heinonen (Eds.), *Mission, vision, strategies, and values : A celebration of translator training and translation studies in Kouvola* (pp. 139 – 148). Helsinki University Press.

- Marais, K. (2021). Tom, Dick and Harry as well as Puss in Boots and Fido are translators: The implications of biosemiotics for translation studies. In O. Caronelli I Cortes & E. Monzo Nebot (Eds.), *Translating Asymmetry/Rewriting Power*. Benjamins, pp. 101-121.
- Marais, K. & Delgado Luchner, C. (2018). Motivating the translation- development nexus: exploring cases from the African Continent, *The Translator*, 24(4), 380-394.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13556509.2019.1594573>
- Nathan, D. & Austin, P. K. (2004). Reconceiving metadata: language documentation through thick and thin. *Language Documentation and Description*, 2, 179-187.
<http://www.elpublishing.org/PID/029>
- Newmark, P. (1988). *A Textbook of Translation*. Prentice Hall.
- Nida, E. A. (1964). *Toward a science of translating*. E. J. Brill.
- Nord, C. (1997). *Translating as a purposeful activity: Functional approaches explained*. St Jerome.
- Nord, C. (2003). Proper names in translations for children. *Meta XLVIII* (1-2), 182-196.
<https://doi.org/10.7202/006966ar>
- Olalla-Soler, C. (2020). Practices and attitudes toward replication in empirical translation and interpreting. *Target. International Journal of Translation Studies*, 32(1), 3-36.
<https://doi.org/10.1075/target.18159.ola>
- O'Shannessy, C., Disbray, S., Martin, B. & MacDonald, G. (2019). (Re)turning research into pedagogical practice: A case study of translational language research in Warlpiri. In L. Barwick, J. Green & P. Vaarzon-Morel (Eds.), Archival Returns: Central Australia and beyond (pp. 139-151). University of Hawaii Press. <http://hdl.handle.net/10125/24881/>.
- Pedersen, J. (2011). *Subtitling norms for television: an exploration focusing on extralinguistic cultural references*. John Benjamins. <https://doi.org/10.1075/btl.98>
- Penfield, S. & Tucker, B. (2011). From documenting to revitalizing an endangered language: Where do applied linguists fit? *Language and Education*, 25(4), 291–305.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/09500782.2011.577219>
- Pym, A. (2000). *Negotiating the frontier: Translators and intercultural history*. Routledge.
- Pym, A. (2012). *On translator ethics: Principles for mediation between cultures*. John Benjamins.
- Ramière, N. (2006). Reaching a foreign audience: cultural transfers in audiovisual translation. *JoSTrans, The Journal of Specialised Translation*, 6, 152-156.
http://www.jostrans.org/issue06/art_ramiere.pdf

- Rice, S. (2011). Applied field linguistics: delivering linguistic training to speakers of endangered languages. *Language and Education*, 25 (4), 319-338.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/09500782.2011.577216>
- Robins, R. H. & Uhlenbeck, E. M. (Eds.). (1991). *Endangered languages*. Berg.
- Roche, G. (2020). Abandoning endangered languages: Ethical loneliness, language oppression, and social justice. *American Anthropologist*, 122(1), 164-169.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/aman.13372>.
- Romaine, S. (2007). Preserving endangered languages. *Language and Linguistics Compass*, 1(1-2), 115-132. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1749-818X.2007.00004.x>
- Rymer, R. (2012, July). Vanishing voices. *National Geographic*, July.
<https://www.nationalgeographic.com/magazine/article/vanishing-languages>
- Saldanha, G. (2008). Explication revisited: Bringing the reader into the picture. *Trans-Kom*, 1(1), 20-35. http://www.trans-kom.eu/ihv_01_01_2008.html
- Saldanha, G. (2011). Style of Translation: The Use of Foreign Words in Translations by Margaret Jull Costa and Peter Bush, In A. Kruger, K. Wallmach & J. Munday (Eds.), *Corpus-based Translation Studies: Research and Applications*. Bloomsbury, pp. 237 – 258.
- Salfner, S. (2015). A Guide to the Ikaan language and culture documentation. *Language Documentation & Conservation*, 9, 237-267. <http://hdl.handle.net/10125/24639>
- Salih, K. (2019). Kurdish linguistic in the 'Saddamist' state. *Genocide Studies International* 13(1), 34 – 51. <https://doi.org/10.3138/gsi.13.1.03>
- Sallabank, J. & King, J. (2021). What do we revitalise? In J. Sallabank and J. Olko (Eds.), *Revitalising endangered languages: A practical guide* (pp. 33-46). Cambridge University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108641142.003>
- Särkkä, H. (2007). Translation of Proper Names in non-fiction texts. *Translation Journal*, 11(1).
<https://translationjournal.net/journal/39proper.htm>
- Schultze-Berndt, E. (2006). Linguistic annotation. In J. Gippert, N. P. Himmelman & U. Mosel (Eds.), *Essentials of Language Documentation*, (pp. 213 – 251). Mouton de Gruyter.
<https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110197730.213>
- Schwartz, S. & Dobrin, L. (2016). The cultures of Native North American language documentation and revitalization. *Reviews in Anthropology*, 45, 88-123.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00938157.2016.1179522>

Translation Studies MA Dissertation

- Shamma, T. (2005). The exotic dimension of foreignizing strategies. *The Translator*, 11(1), 51-67. [10.1080/13556509.2005.10799189](https://doi.org/10.1080/13556509.2005.10799189)
- Skutnabb-Kangas, T. (2000). *Linguistic genocide in education or worldwide diversity and human rights?* Lawrence Erlbaum Associates Publishers.
- Snell-Hornby, M. (1988). *Translation studies: An integrated approach*. John Benjamins. <https://doi.org/10.1075/z.38>
- Sommer, D. (1990). Resistant texts and incompetent readers. *Latin American Literary Review* 20: 40, 16 – 41.
- Stibbe, A. (2020). *Ecolinguistics: Language, ecology and the stories we live by*. Routledge.
- Taibi, M. & Ozolins, U. (2016). *Community translation*. Bloomsbury Academic.
- Taibi, M. (2017). *Translating for the community*. Multilingual Matters. <https://doi.org/10.21832/9781783099146>
- Taylor-Adams, A. (2019). Recording to revitalize: Language teachers and documentation design. *Language Documentation and Conservation*, 13, 426-445. <http://hdl.handle.net/10125/24873>
- Thieberger, N. (Ed.). (2012). *The Oxford Handbook of Linguistic Fieldwork*. OUP. 10.1093/oxfordhb/9780199571888.001.0001
- Toury, G. (1995). *Descriptive translation studies and beyond*. John Benjamins.
- Trompenaars, F. & Hampden-Turner, C. (2012). *Riding the waves of culture. Understanding cultural diversity in business*, 3rd edition. McGraw-Hill.
- Tymoczko, M. (2006). Reconceptualizing Translation Theory: Integrating Non-Western Thought about Translation, in T. Hermans (Ed.) *Translating Others*, St. Jerome, pp. 13–32.
- Tymoczko, M. (2007). *Enlarging Translation, Empowering Translators*. St. Jerome.
- Tymoczko, M. (2009). Why Translators Should Want to Internationalize Translation Studies. *The Translator*, 15(2), 401-421. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13556509.2009.10799287>
- Tymoczko, M. (2010). The space and time of activist translation. In Tymoczko, M. (Ed.) *Translation, Resistance, Activism*, (pp. 227 - 254). University of Massachusetts Press.
- Underriner, J., Marean, L., Keskitalo, P., Zahir, Z., Bommelyn, P. & Tuttle, R. (2021). Teaching Strategies for Language Revitalization and Maintenance. In J. Sallabank & J. Olko (Eds.) *Revitalizing Endangered Languages* (pp. 235-272). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108641142.016>

- Vázquez Ayora, G. (1977). *Introducción a la traductología*. Georgetown U. Press.
- Venuti, L. (1998a). *The Scandals of Translation : Towards an Ethics of Difference*. Routledge.
<https://doi.org/10.7202/002180ar>
- Venuti, L. (1998b). Introduction. *The Translator*, 4(2), 135-144.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13556509.1998.10799016>
- Venuti, L. (2008). *The translator's invisibility: A history of translation*. Routledge (Original work published 1995)
- Venuti, L. (2019). *Contra Instrumentalism: A Translation Polemic*. University of Nebraska Press.
- Vinay, J-P. & Darbelnet, J. (1977). *Stylistique comparée du français et de l'anglais. Méthode de traduction*. Didier (Original work published 1958)
- Woodbury, A. C. (2003). Defining documentary linguistics. *Language Documentation and Description*, 1, 35-51. <http://www.elpublishing.org/PID/006>
- Woodbury, A. C. (2007). On thick translation in linguistic documentation. *Language Documentation and Description*, 4, 12-135. <http://www.elpublishing.org/PID/052>
- Woodbury, A. C. (2011). Language documentation. In P. K. Austin and J. Sallabank (Eds.), *The Cambridge Handbook of Endangered Languages* (pp. 159-186). Cambridge University Press.
- Yamada, R-M. (2011). Integrating documentation and formal teaching of Kari'nja: Documentary materials as pedagogical materials. *Language Documentation & Conservation*, 5, 1-30.
<http://hdl.handle.net/10125/4486>
- Zarei, R. & Norouzi, S. (2014). Proper Nouns in translation: Should they be translated? *International Journal of Applied Linguistics & English Literature*, 3(6), 152-161.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.7575/aiac.ijalel.v.3n.6p.152>

Appendices

Appendix 1 – Guide to ELAR references

Whenever text from the corpus is cited, the origin of that text is given in brackets, directly under the citation. Following ELAR conventions (described in Salfner, 2014), the reference includes the name of the researcher, year of deposit, name of the bundle, and the time stamp of the beginning of the specific lexical item, aligned to the original audio(-visual) text, making the references fully verifiable. This is illustrated in example 1, where the text is taken from 1 minute and 18.144 seconds into the audio(-visual) file, ‘yaqay-olsson-0552’, in the 2021 deposit by Olsson. The lexical item under discussion is printed in **bold type**. This ensures that the data is verifiable, and ensures transparency about how to locate the examples used in the research (Berez-Kroeker *et al.*, 2018).

Example 1	Proper Nouns (place)
ST	Qatan aqan kedekaqan nan-pämbrok Qatan aqan anoq
gloss	Qatan to hither:I FUT-3PL-LOC-put Qatan to 1sg
TT	"I'll go to Qatan , then they'll take me to this place"
(Olsson2021,0005-Linus.00:01:18.144)	

Appendix 2: ELAR Deposits surveyed for Study 1

- Döhler, C. (2019). *A comprehensive documentation of Bine: A language of Southern New Guinea*. Endangered Languages Archive. <http://hdl.handle.net/2196/00-0000-0000-0010-897F-A>
- Gonzales Castaño, G. (2015). *Documentation and Description of Nam Trik, an endangered language of the Colombian Andes*. Endangered Languages Archive. <http://hdl.handle.net/2196/00-0000-0000-000F-72B1-3>
- Li, Y. (2017). *Documentation of Zauzou, an endangered language in China*. Endangered Languages Archive. <http://hdl.handle.net/2196/00-0000-0000-0010-8822-7>
- Martinez, P. A. (2020). *Documentary Corpus of Chhitkul-Rakchham, an endangered Tibeto-Burman language of Northern India – Himachal Pradesh, Kinnaur District*. Endangered Languages Archive. <http://hdl.handle.net/2196/00-0000-0000-0012-40DE-C>
- Olsson, B. (2021). *Documentation of Yaqay, an Anim language of Papua, Indonesia*. Endangered Languages Archive. <http://hdl.handle.net/2196/00-0000-0000-0012-6E04-6>
- Ozerov, P. (2018). *A community-driven documentation of natural discourse in Anal, an endangered Tibeto-Burman language*. <http://hdl.handle.net/2196/00-0000-0000-000F-CB55-6>
- Perlin, R. (2018). *Documenting Seke Stories*. Endangered Languages Archive. <http://hdl.handle.net/2196/00-0000-0000-0012-436C-E>
- Pick, A. (2020). *Gildipasi language project: tumbuna stories and tumbuna knowledge*. Endangered Languages Archive. <http://hdl.handle.net/2196/00-0000-0000-0012-D794-8>
- Rangelov, T. (2020). *Documenting Ahamb, a Small Island Language of Vanuatu*. Endangered Languages Archive. <http://hdl.handle.net/2196/00-0000-0000-000F-E780-0>

Appendix 3: List of references for the text corpus for Study 2

- Dohler, C., Jiri, T. & Jami, L. (2019). Kubuyam saba: bon20180207_02. In *A comprehensive documentation of Bine: A language of Southern New Guinea*. Endangered Languages Archive. https://www.eltarchive.org/uncategorized/so_04045163-58ba-4347-9613-41650875b943/
- Li, Y., Yang, L. & Li, L-M. (2017). Zauzou marriage: YangLiZhong02. In *Documentation of Zauzou, an endangered language in China*. Endangered Languages Archive. https://www.eltarchive.org/index.php?name=so_5471908f-0994-4fa8-8369-be442beb150d
- Li, Y. & Li, L-M. (2017). Raising pigs: LiLiMei02. In *Documentation of Zauzou, an endangered language in China*. Endangered Languages Archive. https://www.eltarchive.org/uncategorized/SO_585e68e8-668f-4788-ae48-7dc0e2765a3e/
- Li, Y., Li, L. & Li, L-M. (2017). Red wine: Cooking01. In *Documentation of Zauzou, an endangered language in China*. Endangered Languages Archive. https://www.eltarchive.org/uncategorized/SO_0adf3dfc-7cfe-4e05-8544-f457d14ebc14/
- Li, Y., Yang, L. & Li, L-M. (2017). Repair pipe: Conversation02. *Documentation of Zauzou, an endangered language in China*. Endangered Languages Archive. https://www.eltarchive.org/index.php?name=SO_ace9b0a2-049a-4d6e-915f-df3cf5a63e91
- Li, Y, Chu, R. & Li, Y. (2017). Making Zauzou shoes: ChuRuiNiang08. *Documentation of Zauzou, an endangered language in China*. Endangered Languages Archive. https://www.eltarchive.org/uncategorized/so_4f80be27-a658-4b7d-8579-2de76f1971b0/
- Li, Y., Yang, S-S. & Li, L-M. (2017). Ghost festival: YangShuShan15. *Documentation of Zauzou, an endangered language in China*. Endangered Languages Archive. <http://hdl.handle.net/2196/00-0000-0000-0012-4A8C-A>
- Li, Y., Yang, S-S. & Li, L-M. (2017). Transformation from a frog: YangShuShan13. *Documentation of Zauzou, an endangered language in China*. Endangered Languages Archive. <http://hdl.handle.net/2196/00-0000-0000-0012-4A8E-5>
- Martinez, P. A., Singh, S. & Negi, N-P. (2020). Gunsaa: TRD_cik10SS120190411. *Documentary Corpus of Chhitkul-Rakchham, an endangered Tibeto-Burman language of Northern India –*

Himachal Pradesh, Kinnaur District. Endangered Languages Archive.

https://www.elararchive.org/uncategorized/so_ac0cac51-d064-45fc-80a9-ccee2fb32a50/

Martinez, P. A., Devi, G., Negi, N-P. & Singh, A. (2020). A local dish called hot:

TRD_cik04GD20181126. *Documentary Corpus of Chhitkul-Rakchham, an endangered Tibeto-Burman language of Northern India – Himachal Pradesh, Kinnaur District*. Endangered Languages Archive. https://www.elararchive.org/uncategorized/so_c7c4271c-85bf-4fc7-98ca-33b67d2d0b5d/

Martinez, P. A., Bhakti, S. & Negi, N-P. (2020). Shiv Bhakti's experience at school:

AUT_cik13SB220181125. *Documentary Corpus of Chhitkul-Rakchham, an endangered Tibeto-Burman language of Northern India – Himachal Pradesh, Kinnaur District*.

Endangered Languages Archive. https://www.elararchive.org/uncategorized/so_431651aa-65a6-4903-9010-1802281469fa/

Martinez, P. A., Kumari, Devi, S. & Negi, N-P. (2020). Collecting pine leaves in Rakchham:

TOP_cik07MK20181127. *Documentary Corpus of Chhitkul-Rakchham, an endangered Tibeto-Burman language of Northern India – Himachal Pradesh, Kinnaur District*. Endangered Languages Archive. https://www.elararchive.org/uncategorized/so_79ce85d0-a71d-46d7-8ea2-6c178a861a27/

Martinez, P. A., Lal, J., Chander, J. & Negi, N-P. (2020). The origins of Mata Devi:

TRD_cik03JL20181125. *Documentary Corpus of Chhitkul-Rakchham, an endangered Tibeto-Burman language of Northern India – Himachal Pradesh, Kinnaur District*. Endangered Languages Archive. https://www.elararchive.org/uncategorized/so_f3095a58-24c7-4e0b-8608-05aa4295b7fe/

Olsson, B. & Tamkoimu, L. (2021). The Journeys of the Priests: 0005-Linus. *Documentation of Yaqay, an Anim language of Papua, Indonesia*. Endangered Languages Archive.

https://www.elararchive.org/uncategorized/SO_c9b51fc4-6948-4d1f-8b43-22dec0a7bbba/

Ozerov, P. (2018). Mithun: anm_20151123_Solhring_PO_Mithun. *A community-driven*

documentation of natural discourse in Anal, an endangered Tibeto-Burman language.

https://www.elararchive.org/uncategorized/SO_e4d5ccc1-7c92-42f5-9861-fe5f2a753f55/

Perlin, R., Dhundul, K & Gurung, R. (2018). A storyteller's memory: SKJ_2019_08_16C. *Documenting Seke Stories*. Endangered Languages Archive.

https://www.elararchive.org/uncategorized/SO_000a1fcd-741d-45bf-bdf2-7a7240c0cbe9/

Appendix 4 – Sample of Translation Strategies used for rendering Cultural Terms

1. Retention

Example 1	Proper Nouns (person)
ST	pasang biwa me sherpa
Gloss	pasang say Sherpa
TT	someone called Sherpa Pasang

(Perlin2018,SKJ_2019_08_16c.00:24:14.912)

Example 2	Proper Nouns (place)
ST	Qatan aqan kedekaqan nan-pämbrok Qatan aqan anoq
gloss	Qatan to hither:I FUT-3PL-LOC-put Qatan to 1sg
TT	"I'll go to Qatan , then they'll take me to this place"

(Olsson2021,yaqay-olsson-0552.00:01:18.144)

Example 3	Measurement
ST	de31 qong55 de55 ve13 nai33 a55si55 jin33 nga31 a31 u13 u13si13 jin33 nga33 a31 u13
Gloss	one CL.jar DEM.DIST CL TOP 20 MW.jin know NEG RES.successful 50
TT	MW.jin know NEG RES.successful It's not known if a jar is 20 jin or 50 jin

(Li & Li, 2017,YangLiZhong02.00:04:31.405)

Example 4	Cultural object/practice
ST	dahal mar bize langbin
gloss	Dahal mar say.tell play
TT	We also played dahal mar

(Perlin2018,SKJ_2019_08_16c.00:40:48.512)

Example 5	Cultural object/practice
ST	Dangba nu shapro
gloss	First FOC shapro
TT	we danced shapro

(Perlin2018,SKJ_2019_08_16c.01:05:12.343)

Example 6	Cultural object/practice
ST	dangbo kalo ri ken yoli nalza
gloss	long.ago era LOC food stir pot.small
TT	those pots were used to make as nalza

(Perlin2018,SKJ_2019_08_16c.00:16:18.420)

Example 7 Proper nouns (person)
 ST **guru rinpoche**
 gloss **Guru rinpoche**
 TT **Guru Rinpoche**

(Perlin2018,SKJ_2019_08_16c.00:00:49.920)

Example 8 Proper Nouns (place)
 ST **Phunchung** nahangphatiing **Lambungru phumchung** alāng
 Gloss **PN** 1DL-go.up-reach-before **PN**-and **PN** between
 TT Just before we reached **Phunchung**, between **Lambung** and **Phunchung**.

(Ozerov2018),anm_20151123_Solhring_PO_Mithun.00:01:23.369)

Example 9 Dish
 ST **alu sabzi** raj hot ta bã mã nimi a:ts
 gloss **potato sabzi** with chilte is very tasty happen/become
 TT Chilta is very tasty with **alu sabzi**

(Martinez et al.2020, TRD_cik04GD20181126.00:07:46.710)

Example 10 Ingredient
 ST Char rupe ko kati **mana** ho bim
 gloss There boil to.get.lost, disappear **mana** Say.tell IMP
 TT How many **mana** for four rupees?

(Perlin2018,SKJ_2019_08_16c.00:17:59.895)

2. Specification

Example 11 Kinship
 ST Sherka niwa **nyezangza** hadona yarzi da lo chi nga
 Gloss Two **family.ally** meet.go now year four I (1SG)
 TT It's been 4-5 years since I've met my **nyezang (family allies)**

(Perlin2018,SKJ_2019_08_16c.00:14:49.426)

Example 12 Proper Noun
 ST dini **guru rinpoche** nu
 Gloss And **guru Rinpoche** FOC
 TT So this **Guru Rinpoche** [the culture hero also called Padmasambhawa, credited with bringing Buddhism to Tibet)

(Perlin2018,SKJ_2019_08_16c.00:00:16.686)

- Example 13** Proper Nouns (place)
 ST Ure gome “agesi nunde tasura”
 Gloss
 TT at **ure gome** (he said) "here is another tasura"
Translator comment = placename

(Dohler et al.2019,bon20180207_02.00:02:38.940)

- Example 14** Ecological
 ST tonete bi bagrige **mrusi gare**
 Gloss
 TT the sharp stick killed them from the **mrusi tree**
 Translator notes: **mrusi = tree type; gare= thorn**

(Dohler et al.2019,bon20180207_02.00:05:28.383)

- Example 15** Measurements
 ST **pathi** ko kati bize hamem
 gloss **Pathi** boil say.tell PROG NEG full.satisfied
 TT We didn't ask how much for a **pathi (unit of volume)**

(Perlin2018,SKJ_2019_08_16c.00:17:47.826)

- Example 16** People (nationality)
 ST Boong biza langma tsuwa **khampa** ze dangze langziwa le bar
 gloss Boong say.tell word tsuwa **khampa** ERG then langziwa quickly
 take.away
 TT And then playing Boong was invented by the **Khampas (Tibetans)**

(Perlin2018,SKJ_2019_08_16c.00:41:29.609)

- Example 17** Ecological
 ST Nima taa **ku taktak** bize sepa hayinba tsiri
 Gloss Bird what pot **ku taktak** say.tell kill here.
 TT **Ku taktaks (bird species)** are killed here.

(Perlin2018,SKJ_2019_08_16c.00:38:14.237)

- Example 18** Cultural object/practice
 ST gola gola konze **arti** pungze kon thowa
 gloss clothes clothes wear then **special.ceremonial dress**
 TT wearing ... **arti (clothing worn during celebrations)**

(Perlin2018,SKJ_2019_08_16c.00:22:48.797)

Example 19 Cultural object/practice
 ST bize hozi guru rinpoche **dorje** namze birze phenuwa gangdi
 gloss Say.tell and guru Rinpoche **dorje** go EXHON when
 TT Rinpoche brought out his **dorje (ritual "thunderbolt" battle club)**

(Perlin2018,SKJ_2019_08_16c.00:02:16.275)

Example 20 Cultural object/practice
 ST **yartong** lawa
 Gloss horse-racing festival do
 TT and **yartong (the horse-racing festival)**

(Perlin2018,SKJ_2019_08_16c.00:22:43.963)

Example 21 Cultural object/practice
 ST **gunsa:** teotfo buzurukt[ane] tamtji dzua tsoro han toa
 hojo tʰɛtiŋ **gunsa:** roa njo
 Gloss **Gunsa** ABS before LOC elder PL GEN time ABL
 TT **Gunsa:** There is more snow here, due to that, the elders used to go for
Gunsa:
 note: **Gunsa: refers to is a process or tradition in the whole Kinnaur District whereby people 'migrate' to warmer locations during winter season.**

(Martinez2020, TRD_cik10SS120190411.00:00:05.100)

Example 22 Cultural object/practice
 ST **taktsa** biwin baagra jangra
 Gloss taktsa say, tell tiger goat
 TT and [we would play] also **taktsa (game of tiger and goats)**

(Perlin2018,SKJ_2019_08_16c.00:30:40.009)

3. Direct Translation

Example 23 People
 ST **i33 bei55**
 Gloss **Aunt PL**
 TT **Aunties**

(Li & Li 2017,YangLiZhong02.00:11:21.102)

Example 24 Measurements
 ST i35 na53 ei35 bang35
 gloss wine **two bowl** take
 TT Take **two bowls** of wine

(Li & Li 2017, YangLiZhong02.00:02:35.233)

Example 25
 ST **Dadu** kanang kanang nyo pungna
 gloss **Cooking.spoon** kanyang kanyang milk hit
 TT they put **two spatula's worth** of milk

(Perlin2018,SKJ_2019_08_16c.00:19:14.843)

Example 26 MEASUREMENTS
 ST I55ban55 **jou33zang33** va55 mi55
 Gloss Normally **wine dreg** feed much
 TT we feed them with **wine dregs**

(Li & Li 2017, LiLiMei02.00:03:51.773)

Example 27
 ST **Za**
 Gloss **Son**
 TT **Son**

(Perlin2018,SKJ_2019_08_16c.00:47:06.446)

4. Generalisation

Example 28
 ST kege ma mame tasura gome deteri ka ka tasura deterine.
 gloss Same sized brother
 TT Brother, you go to your fishtrap. I go to my fishtrap

(Dohler et al.2019,bon20180207_02.00:03:11.608)

Example 29 Cultural Object/Practice
 ST **zong**
 gloss **Hole.borer**
 TT **hole borer**

(Perlin2018,SKJ_2019_08_16c.00:03:16.903)

Example 30 Cultural Object/Practice
 ST **Tho**
 gloss **Large.bronze.vessel**

TT **Pot**
 (Perlin2018,SKJ_2019_08_16c.00:03:03.966)

Example 31 Cultural Object/Practice
 ST **qou33gy55** lai31 a55sen33 **tou33**
 gloss **hammer** CL DEM.PROX **hull rice**
 TT
 (Li & Li 2017,YangShuShan13.00:04:55.225)

5. Linguistic Substitution

Example 32 Measurement
 ST Cei55 nai53 **lo55** de31 jou55 nen55
 gloss Ten two MW.pai one CL.string need
 TT we need hair which is **12 pai-long**
 (Li & Li 2017,YangShuShan13.00:12:46.446)

Example 33 Cultural Object/Practice
 ST Ai31 de55 hang13 nai55 du55 de 55 **Den13** de31 lai31qi13 ia13ve13
 gloss ai Dem.DIST very TOP 3 3 **sanxian** one CL have so
 TT At that time he has a **sanxian**
 (Li & Li 2017,YangShuShan13.00:05:45.702)

Example 34 Cultural Object/Practice
 ST **Dasa ri**
 gloss **Dasa ri**
 TT **The Dashain holiday**
 (Perlin2018,SKJ_2019_08_16c.00:27:51.449)

6. Official Equivalent

Example 35 Proper Nouns (place)
 ST **Zongsambaze**
 gloss **Jomsom**
 TT **Jomsom**
 (Perlin2018,SKJ_2019_08_16c.00:00:23.570)

Example 36 Ecological
 ST **mia55tsẽ55**
 Gloss **PN.goupi tree**

TT **Goupi tree**
 (Li & Li 2017,Conversation02.00:00:43.279)

Example 37 Measurements
 ST si13ji33 **kuai55**
 gloss more than ten **CL.kuai**
 TT more than ten **Yuan** per day
 (Li & Li 2017,Conversation02.00:06:00.922)

Example 38 Place
 ST Koelaso
 Gloss Koelaso
 TT Mount Kailash
 TN: Koelaso is the Kinnauri name for Kailash mountain area

(Martinez, Chander & Negi,2020, TRD_cik03JL20181125.00:02:24.870)

7. Combinations

Example 39 Food
 ST **Zima** gi yinli
 gloss Zima one
 TT Even if it's **zimbu (wild herb)**
 (Perlin2018,SKJ_2019_08_16c.01:08:00.777)

Example 40 Food
 ST **paa** thungzi ja thungzi
 gloss **rice.wine** drink tea drink
 TT we drank **local chhang (beer)** and tea
 (Perlin2018,SKJ_2019_08_16c.00:19:37.460)

Appendix 5: Sample Source Text

Martinez, P. A., Devi, G., Negi, N-P. & Singh, A. (2020). A local dish called hot.

A_morph-gls-en INTERJ HON younger brother or sister PL
 A_morph-txt-cik-fonipa namaste dʒi baia -tʃaŋ
 A_phrase-gls-en Namaste Jee Younger brothers and sisters
 A_phrase-gls-hi नमस्ते जी छोटे भाई-बहने,
 A_phrase-segnum-en 1 2
 A_word-gls-cik-fonipa hello sir brothers and sisters
 A_word-txt-cik-fonipa namaste dʒi baiaʃaŋ

A_morph-gls-en 1SG ABS resign ABS make INF COP.PEEX PRS bitter buck
 A_morph-txt-cik-fonipa ga: -∅ hɔt -∅ ʈatʃ -aŋ to -∅ brasu
 A_phrase-gls-en I have to cook chilta, bitter/ black buck's chilta
 A_phrase-gls-hi मुझे चिलटा बनाना है, फाफरे का चिलटा,
 A_phrase-note-en Brasu ('bitter buck') is borrowed from Kinnauri
 A_phrase-segnum-en 3
 A_word-gls-cik-fonipa I chilta to make () bitter buck
 A_word-txt-cik-fonipa ga: hɔt ʈatʃaŋ to brasu

A_morph-gls-en resign ABS now make E FUT.DUB 1SG resign ABS
 A_morph-txt-cik-fonipa hɔt -∅ ʈʰa ʈatʃ -i -na -k hɔt -∅
 A_phrase-gls-en Now, I will cook chilta
 A_phrase-gls-hi अब चिलटा बनाऊंगी,
 A_phrase-segnum-en 4
 A_word-gls-cik-fonipa chilta now will cook chilta
 A_word-txt-cik-fonipa hɔt ʈʰa ʈatʃinak hɔt

A_morph-gls-en resign ABS make INF AUX.PEEX PRS today bitter buck
 A_morph-txt-cik-fonipa hɔt -∅ ʈatʃ -aŋ to -∅ ʈʰan brasu
 A_phrase-gls-en I have to cook chilta, today bitter buck chilta, it is
 good
 A_phrase-gls-hi चिलटा बनाना है, आज फाफरे का चिलटा, बढ़िया होत है
 A_phrase-note-en Badʰia is borrowed from Hindi
 A_phrase-segnum-en 5
 A_word-gls-cik-fonipa chilta to make () today bitter buck
 A_word-txt-cik-fonipa hɔt ʈatʃaŋ to ʈʰan brasu

A_morph-gls-en resign ABS good COP HAB.ASS
 A_morph-txt-cik-fonipa hɔt -∅ baɖʰia a: -ts
 A_word-gls-cik-fonipa chilta good happen/become

Declaration

I hereby declare that the text of this dissertation is substantially my own work.

Holly Drayton 01/10/2021